

From cosmic velocity to black
holes to theory
of quantum expansion
of space with the hypothesis of
the action of dark matter that
converts into dark energy

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To avoid confusion in the dimensions in the formulas between meters and mass, we indicate:

meters with = m, r, l, d and the mass in kg with = M

Physical constants will be indicated with the prefix (c.) followed by a number the size of the constants will be indicated on page..... 48

The new constants that emerged from the calculations of this work are indicated by the prefix (Nc.) followed by a number, the dimensions will be indicated on page..... 48

From cosmic velocity to black holes to the theory of the quantum expansion of space with the hypothesis of the action of dark matter that converts into dark energy

The aim of this research is to find an interpretation that describes the dynamics of the expansion of space and to understand the causes of its action. Let's start from the most infinitesimal point, at the quantum level, let's hypothesize that the mechanics of expansion depend on the action of dark matter contained in empty space, which in converting into dark energy creates a work that produces expansion. For this, we look for physical values of the hypothesized dark matter and formulas to calculate its dynamics.

It should be remembered that the expansion of space, predicted by the Belgian physicist and astronomer Georges Lemaitre¹ and observed by the American astronomer Edwin Hubble¹ in the '20s, is the phenomenon by which galaxies move away from each other at a speed proportional to their distance¹, described by the Hubble-Lemaitre Law¹, indicates that the universe is stretching, it has been observed that the galaxies farther away from us are moving away faster¹, a phenomenon observed through Redshift¹, (the redshift of the spectrum of light), is not a movement "through" space, but an expansion of space-time, which lengthens distances. The rate of expansion is calculated with the "Hubble Constant (H_0)"¹.

From the observations it is estimated that the expansion speed of space is between 67.4 and 76.5 km/s¹ per mega parsec, and indicates the current expansion rate, the calculated speed leads to a continuous update of its value, the average reference speed is about 70 km/s¹ per mega parsec¹, its precise value is at the center of a dispute, another method of calculating the velocity is the analysis of the cosmic microwave background radiation (CMB)¹, the echo of the Big Bang, with this measurement the velocity is about 67.4 km/s¹ per mega parsec, both measurements are used to calculate the Hubble Constant (H_0)¹, These are the two main methods, then there are other methods that we will leave out.

A 2025 study led by the Hungarian scientist Balazs Enfre Szigeti¹ of the Wigner Research Center in Hungary and the astronomer Istvan Szapudi¹ of the University of Hawaii, propose a mathematical model that adds to the expansion of the universe also a small rotation¹ (a rotation about every 500 billion years)¹, with this small rotation the difference in the measurement of the expansion rates of space would be solved¹.

Of the universe we know that visible matter, baryonic matter¹, formed by protons, neutrons and electrons represents about 4.9%¹ of the universe¹, then we have dark matter calculated to be 26.8%¹, dark matter is considered to be the glue that binds stars and galaxies¹ to each other and then we have dark energy which represents about 68.3%¹ of the universe, and is considered responsible for space expansion¹. Dark matter and energy do not absorb electromagnetic waves¹, so they remain invisible for now¹; We know of their existence due to the gravitational "glue" effect with which they are presumed to hold galaxies together¹ and which make the stars rotate homogeneously from the center to the periphery of galaxy¹.

Suppose that the action depends on an entropic effect "the molecular disintegration"¹ of an infinitesimal matter, contained in empty space, which slowly converts into energy, at a rate of quantum drives, causing expansion.

The first to postulate a matter with an inverse gravitational action, was the German physicist Arthur Schuster¹ (1851-1934) who first used the term antimatter in 1898¹, hypothesizing the existence of a solar system formed by antimatter in which gravity was also repulsive, with this hypothesis, clusters of antimatter can form black holes with repulsive gravity which would be white holes, the existence of white holes is predicted in Einstein's theory of general relativity, antimatter was experimentally confirmed in 1932¹ by the American physicist Carl David Anderson¹ (1905-1991) , but the discovered antimatter annihilates itself in contact with classical matter by instantly converting into energy¹, consequently it cannot be the intrinsic matter contained in the empty space we are looking for.

In September 2023 in the Alpha-g experiment at CERN ¹ led by Danish physicist Emma K. Anderson¹, antimatter atoms were pulled downwards by classical gravity ¹ refuting Schuster's hypothesis that antimatter was of reverse gravity¹. I wanted to quote Schuster because before 2023 I also assumed that antimatter must have characteristics of reverse gravity.

the term dark matter was first proposed by the Swiss astronomer Fritz Zwicky ¹ (1898-1974). We will work on the hypothesis of its existence, studying its hypothetical characteristics, we will give it a physical value by measuring density, mass, energy and a frequency, we will also give it a symbol Z named after the astronomer Fritz Zwicky in Greek. ζ

Assuming that the law of expansion of dark matter is equal to but inverse to gravity, we will begin the study with the law of universal gravitation, discovered by the English mathematician, physicist and astronomer Isaac Newton¹ (1643-1727). We continue with relativity and the field equation discovered by the German physicist Albert Einstein¹ (1879-1955), moving on to quantum physics discovered by the German physicist Max Planck¹ (1858-1947) and the correct calculation of relativity by the German mathematician and astronomer Karl Schwarzschild¹ (1873-1916), up to the discovery of the expansion of space made by the observation of the American astronomer Edwin Powell Hubble¹ (1889-1953).

We will highlight the relationships between gravity, quantum physics, and general relativity as the universe expands.

This theory is based on the hypothesis that dark matter is present in all empty space, including interatomic space, between electrons and protons, which expands at every point with a quantum rate at a constant speed, from observations it is assumed that the expansion of space acts in all spatial directions at the same time, consequently the observer sees an acceleration of the celestial objects observed in space.

Gravity and cosmic velocity act in different spatial directions, the expansion of space acts with the same laws as cosmic velocity only with different results, the actions are distinguished by the characteristics listed below.

The first action caused by the masses is the force of gravity, it is the best known, it is caused by the mass (M), it is a force (F) whose value is the product of the masses (M) of two bodies, by the gravitational constant (G) divided by the squared distance between the two masses (M); The force of gravity decreases to the square of the distance of the two masses, like the radiation of heat in the law of thermodynamics, the direction of action of the resulting force is perpendicular towards the center of the two masses, the action is observed with the fall of objects towards the center of the masses.

The second action caused by mass is the cosmic velocity, the value of which is the square root of the product of a mass (M) by the gravitational constant (G) divided by the distance from the center of the mass, the direction of action is radial with respect to the center of the mass and the cosmic velocity squared does not decrease as the distance increases but its decrease is directly proportional to the product, between the gravitational constant, by the mass, divided by the distance. Cosmic velocity is the result of space-time deformation caused by masses.

The cosmic velocity squared divided by the distance from the center of gravity indicates the value of gravitational acceleration. (g) is measured in Newtons.

The value of cosmic velocity, used in the formula of special relativity by Einstein and Schwarzschild, defines the deformation of space-time, caused by mass, with cosmic velocity, placed at the limit of the speed of light; The size and masses of black holes can be calculated. The action of cosmic velocity is observed in the motions of planets and satellites around their center of gravity. For larger objects, see stars and galaxies where the mass prevents the orbit of one around the other, the result of the cosmic velocity produced by the two masses becomes the speed of approach, practically the two objects glide, towards each other, in their deformation of space-time caused by their masses.

The third action, is the speed of expansion of space, is calculated with the same formula as the cosmic speed, the speed of expansion increases with distance, space expands in all directions, the fact that the speed of expansion increases with distance suggests that empty space contains peculiar physical characteristics, which with the increase in volume causes the acceleration of the expansion of the same, the action is observed with the escape of the galaxies.

(1.0) Newton and the formulas of universal gravitation.

We report the formulas discovered and elaborated by Newton for the force of gravity (F) and the acceleration of gravity (g).

$$F = M \cdot g$$

$$F = G \frac{M_1 \cdot M_2}{r^2} \quad (1.1)$$

The value is the product of the mass of two bodies times the gravitational constant divided by the square of the distance between the two bodies.

Formulas for Gravitational Acceleration $M \cdot g = G \frac{M_1 \cdot M_2}{r^2}$; $g = G \frac{M}{r^2}$

In which (g) is the gravitational acceleration measured in Newtons, (G) it is the universal gravitational constant, (M) it is the mass in kg and (r) is the radius, it indicates the distance in meters.

$$G = 6,67259 \times 10^{-11} \frac{m^3}{kg \cdot s^2} \quad (c.2)$$

For our research we look for cosmic velocity (vc), cosmic velocity is the speed with which celestial bodies and satellites orbit around their center of gravity, it is visible, measurable and calculable. With the formulas (1.2) and (1.3), remember that we look for a force and a speed of expansion, and an acceleration of gravity in relation to the cosmic velocity, we no longer calculate the product between the two masses (M) as in (1.1) but we refer only to the mass of the center of gravity, practically the cosmic velocity indicates the deformation of space-time created by the mass.

The equation for calculating cosmic velocity (vc), radius (r) for distance and mass (M)

$$(vc)^2 \cdot r = G \cdot M \quad (1.2)$$

where is the cosmic velocity squared, (vc)² r is the distance in meters from the center of gravity, is the gravitational constant G (c.2) is $6.67259 \times 10^{-11} \frac{m^3}{kg \cdot s^2}$ and is the mass (M) in kg, we rewrite the formula by displaying only the dimensions;

$$(vc)^2 \cdot r = G \cdot M ; \left(\frac{m}{s}\right)^2 \cdot m = \frac{m^3}{kg \cdot s^2} \cdot kg ; \frac{m^2}{s^2} \cdot m = \frac{m^3}{s^2} ; \frac{m^3}{s^2} = \frac{m^3}{s^2}$$

The formula for finding cosmic velocity (vc): $vc = \sqrt{\frac{G \cdot M}{r}} \quad (1.3)$

for the acceleration of gravity (g) the new equation is, cosmic velocity squared divided by radius (r) from the center of gravity, the result is a centripetal force whose value is expressed in Newtons.

$$\text{Acceleration force in Newtons } g = \frac{(vc)^2}{r} \quad (1.4)$$

(2.0.0) The cosmic velocity (v_C) to calculate the gravitational acceleration on the Earth's surface " g "

Let's check equations (1.2) and (1.3) expressed in chapter (1.0). Let's take some practical examples, let's start by calculating the cosmic velocity (v_C) on the earth's surface and the relative acceleration of gravity resulting (g), in addition to the constant (G)(c.2) we need the mass of the earth (MT) and the average radius of the earth (rT), let's take the related data.

$$\text{Universal gravitational constant } G = 6.67259 \times 10^{-11} \frac{m^3}{kg \cdot s^2} \quad (c.2)$$

$$\text{Earth Mass } MT = 5.972 \times 10^{24} kg^1 \quad (2.0.1)$$

$$\text{Average Earth Radius } rT = 6\,371\,000 \text{ m}^1 \quad (2.0.2)$$

Let's take the formula (1.2) $(v_C)^2 \cdot rT = G \cdot MT$

$$\text{And the formula for Calculating Cosmic Velocity } v_C = \sqrt{\frac{G \cdot MT}{rT}} \quad (1.3)$$

We transcribe the values in the formula (1.3) making the relative calculation we find the average cosmic velocity on the earth's surface;

$$\text{Cosmic speed on the Earth's surface} = \sqrt{\frac{6,67259 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 5,972 \times 10^{24}}{6\,371\,000}} = 7\,908,66 \frac{m}{s} \quad (2.0.3)$$

With the result (2.0.3) of the average cosmic velocity, we calculate the acceleration of gravity with the formula, (1.4) remember that the result is a centripetal force,

$$g = \frac{(v_C)^2}{r} \quad \text{Average gravity acceleration on the Earth's surface}$$

$$g = \frac{(7\,908,66)^2}{6\,371\,000} = 9.81 \frac{m}{s^2} \quad \text{Newtons} \quad (2.0.4)$$

The result (2.0.4) is the average gravitational acceleration on the Earth's surface, we can say that, since the cosmic velocity on the Earth's surface is $7\,908.66 \frac{m}{s}$, all objects with mass on the Earth's surface are attracted to the center of the Earth with an average acceleration of $9.81 \frac{m}{s^2}$. Practically an object, with mass, which moves on the earth's surface at a speed greater than $7.91 \frac{km}{s}$ it should escape gravitational acceleration.

(2.1.0) The cosmic velocity of the Moon

We calculate the cosmic speed of the Moon, from observations we know that the Moon orbits the Earth once every 27.3 days¹ (sidereal month). To make the calculation we need the average Earth-Moon distance, since the Moon orbits the Earth in an elliptical way, by convention the Average

Distance (DTL)= 384.400.000 meters¹ , we also need the mass of the Earth $MT = 5.972 \times 10^{24} \text{kg}^1$ (2.0.1) and the gravitational constant (c.2) $G = 6.67259 \times 10^{-11}$ Once the relative values are obtained, we calculate the cosmic speed (νC) on the orbit of the Moon, with the formula (1.3)

$$\nu C \text{ Moon} = \sqrt{\frac{G \cdot MT}{DTL}} \text{ Let's enter the values} = \sqrt{\frac{6.67259 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 5.972 \times 10^{24}}{384\,400\,000}} = 1\,018.16 \frac{m}{s} \quad (2.1.1)$$

Once we have found the cosmic speed of the Moon, we compare it with the observed revolution times, how many days it takes for the Moon to orbit the Earth, divide the circumference of the orbit by the calculated cosmic speed (2.1.1).

$$\frac{\text{Moon orbit circumference}}{\text{Moon cosmic speed}} = \frac{(2 \cdot 384\,400\,000) \cdot 3.14}{1\,018.16} = \frac{2\,415\,256\,432}{1\,018.16} = 2\,372\,181 \text{ Seconds}$$

$$\text{Once the seconds are found, we divide by seconds} \cdot \text{hours} = \frac{2\,372\,181}{3\,600 \cdot 24} = 27.46 \text{ days} \quad (2.1.2)$$

The result (2.1.2) and compatible with the comments 27.3 days¹, remember that the Moon will orbit in an elliptical way, while the calculation was made on a circular orbit, so the result returns approximate.

(2.2.0) The Earth's cosmic velocity

Applying the formula (1.4), we calculate the speed with which the Earth orbits the Sun, we derive the average distance between the Earth and the Sun (DTS)

$$\text{Average distance between Earth and Sun (DTS)} = 1.496 \times 10^{11} \text{ meters}^1 \quad (2.2.1)$$

$$\text{Mass of the Sun (MS)} = 1.989 \times 10^{30} \text{kg}^1 \quad (2.2.2)$$

$$\text{Let's take up the constant } G = 6.67259 \times 10^{-11} \quad (c.2)$$

Speed of revolution of the earth around the sun, $\nu C \text{ Earth} = \sqrt{\frac{G \cdot MS}{DTS}}$, We enter the values;

$$\nu C \text{ Earth} = \sqrt{\frac{6.67259 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 1.989 \times 10^{30}}{1.496 \times 10^{11}}} = 29\,785.66 \frac{m}{s} \quad (2.2.3)$$

Velocity of revolution of the earth around the official Sun 29.8 km/s¹ Calculated speed 29 785.66 $\frac{m}{s}$. Recall that the earth also orbits the Sun elliptically.

(2.3.0) From the observation of the cosmic velocity of the stars on the outskirts of the Milky Way, we calculate the mass of the galaxy

By observing the speed of movement of the stars at the outskirts of our galaxy, we try to estimate the mass of the Milky Way. Let's make a mention of what the Milky Way represents, it is the galaxy where the solar system is located with the Earth and all its planets, the position of the solar system is located about halfway through the radius of the galaxy about between 26 000¹ and 27 000¹ light years from the center of the galaxy, the Milky Way has a spiral structure, called the Barred Spiral Galaxy type, is composed of several hundred billion stars¹, is estimated to be between 200 and 400 billion stars¹, has a diameter between 100 000 and 110 000 light-years¹ with an average radius of 52 800 light-years¹, although the galaxy is flattened in the region of the arms it has the thickness of 1 000 light years¹ it includes a gaseous disk of 12 000 light years¹, its mass is estimated to be 200 billion times¹ the mass of the Sun, the speed with which they rotate around the center of the Milky Way is the same for stars that rotate from the center of the radius to the periphery of the galaxy¹, whose speed is estimated to be between 220 km/s¹ and 240 km/s¹. For example, the solar system, which is located at the center of the radius of the galaxy, moves with the same speed as a star on its periphery, we do not know why, it is assumed that this depends on the "glue effect" of dark matter¹, we suppose that in part it could depend on the fact that the galaxy does not have an empty inner space, as between the Earth and the Moon or between the Earth and the Sun, so we calculate the cosmic velocity at the periphery of the galaxy as if the galaxy had a full structure, take the known data and make the related calculations as if the mass were homogeneously distributed without empty space.

By convention, the average radius of the Milky Way is taken as the distance of 52 850 light years¹, we convert them into meters, multiply the speed of light by a year seconds.

$$\text{Speed of Light } C = 299\,792\,458 \text{ meters per second} \quad (\text{c.1})$$

$$\text{a year seconds} = 31\,536\,000 \text{ seconds} \quad (\text{c.9})$$

$$\text{A light year} = 31\,536\,000 \cdot 299\,792\,458 = 9.45425 \times 10^{15} \text{ meters}^1 \quad (\text{c.10})$$

$$\text{Galaxy Beam Length} = 52\,850 \cdot 9.45425 \times 10^{15} = 4.9965 \times 10^{20} \text{ meters} \quad (2.3.1)$$

$$\text{We calculate the average rotation speed } v_c = \frac{220\,000 + 2\,000}{2} = 230\,000 \text{ meters/seconds} \quad (2.3.2)$$

Using the formula (1.2), $(v_c)^2 \cdot r = G \cdot M$, we calculate the estimated mass of the Milky Way, we know (v_c) , r and G let's set the formula

$$\text{Estimated galaxy mass, } M = \frac{(v_c)^2 \cdot r}{G} = \frac{(230\,000)^2 \cdot 4.9965 \times 10^{20}}{6.67259 \times 10^{-11}} = 3.9612 \times 10^{41} \text{ kg} \quad (2.3.3)$$

$$\text{Let's compare the ratio to the mass of the sun} = 1.989 \times 10^{30} \text{ kg.}^1 \quad (2.2.2)$$

$$\text{ratio} = \frac{\text{galaxy mass}}{\text{Sun mass}} = \frac{3.9612 \times 10^{41}}{1.989 \times 10^{30}} = 199\,158\,455\,748 \text{ volte} \quad (2.3.4)$$

The result of the calculation (2.3.4) is perfectly compatible with predictions that the total mass of the Milky Way is about 200 billion¹ times the mass of the Sun.

(2.4.0) The cosmic speeds interacting between the Milky Way and Andromeda galaxies

From the mass of the Milky Way (2.3.3) we calculate the cosmic velocity acting on our nearest galaxy Andromeda. First let's make a mention of the Andromeda galaxy, it too like ours is a barred spiral galaxy¹, it is the closest galaxy to the Milky Way, the distance from the Milky Way is estimated to be between 2,534 and 2,546 million light years¹ its size is larger, its diameter is between 150 000 and 200 000 light years¹ and its mass is estimated to be 1.23×10^{12} times the mass of the Sun. From the observation of Blueshift¹ (of the light spectrum) we know that the two galaxies are approaching at a speed of about 100-140 km per second¹. The value of the sum of the two cosmic velocities is due to the spacetime deformation caused by their masses, the resulting cosmic velocity is the speed of approach.

Let's start by converting the distance between the two galaxies into meters. Let's take 2.54 million light-years as a distance¹, knowing that the distance of a light-year is 9.45425×10^{15} meters.

$$\text{Galaxies distance} = 2.54 \times 10^6 \cdot 9.45425 \times 10^{15} = 2.40138 \times 10^{22} \text{ meters} \quad (2.4.1)$$

$$\text{Cosmic Speed } vc1 \text{ the exerts the Milky Way on Andromeda} = \sqrt{\frac{G \cdot \text{Milky Way mass}}{\text{Galaxies distance}}} =$$

$$vc1 \text{ Andromeda} = \sqrt{\frac{6.67259 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 3.9612 \times 10^{41}}{2.40138 \times 10^{22}}} = 33 \ 176.72 \text{ meters per second} \quad (2.4.2)$$

We calculate the mass of Andromeda to calculate the cosmic speed it exerts on the Milky Way, we know that Andromeda is 1.23×10^{12} times¹ the mass of the Sun, the mass of the Sun is 1.989×10^{30} kg¹

$$\text{Mass Andromeda} = 1.23 \times 10^{12} \cdot 1.989 \times 10^{30} \text{ kg} = 2.6851 \times 10^{42} \text{ kg} \quad (2.4.3)$$

Calculating cosmic velocity $vc2$ exercising Andromeda on the Milky Way;

$$vc2 \text{ Milky Way} = \sqrt{\frac{6.67259 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 2.6851 \times 10^{42}}{2.40138 \times 10^{22}}} = 86 \ 377.57 \text{ meters per second} \quad (2.3.8)$$

Let's add up the two cosmic speeds;

$$vc1 + vc2 = 33 \ 176.72 + 86 \ 377.57 = 119 \ 554.29 \text{ meters per second} \quad (2.4.4)$$

From the result of the sum of the two cosmic velocities (2.4.4), The two galaxies should approach at a speed of about 120 km/s, theoretically the cosmic velocity evolves radially with respect to the center of gravity, but given the mass of the two galaxies it is impossible for them to rotate around each other, so of the deformation of spacetime, the two galaxies slide towards each other in the curvature of spacetime caused by their mass.

(3.0.0) The deformation of space-time in relation to cosmic velocity, calculated with the formula of special relativity

Let's verify the relationship of the deformation of spacetime, in relation to cosmic speed. With the formulas of special relativity, we calculate the time difference due to relativity between two points in space that are on the same radius, but at different distances from the center of gravity, the value of their cosmic velocities are different. From the formula (1.2) it can be deduced that the cosmic speed varies according to distance, so we introduce in the calculation the formula of time dilation of Einstein's special relativity.

$$\text{Formula for time dilation } \Delta t = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\left(\frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)}} \Delta t' \quad (3.0.1)$$

Let's also take Karl Schwarzschild's formula, which calculated the exact solution of the equation of relativity of Einstein¹. The Schwarzschild radius (r_s)¹ or gravitational radius¹ is a characteristic radius associated with each mass¹, is the ray of no return¹, the event horizon of black holes¹. We will need it to calculate the maximum limit of cosmic velocity. Let's see how he set up the formula Schwarzschild; he took the formula of Potential Energy and made the equivalence with kinetic energy¹,

practically
$$E_{\text{Kinetic}} = E_{\text{Potential}}$$

Potential Energy Formula; $-\frac{GMm}{r}$ Kinetic Energy Formula; $\frac{1}{2}mv^2$

which becomes; $\frac{1}{2}mv^2 = \frac{GMm}{r}$; which becomes; $\frac{1}{2}v^2 = \frac{GM}{r}$; which becomes; $v = \sqrt{\frac{2GM}{r}}$

replaces velocity v with c (c.1); $c = \sqrt{\frac{2GM}{r_s}}$ which becomes; $r_s = \frac{2G}{c^2}M$ (3.0.2)

In which (r_s) is the radius of Schwarzschild expressed in meters and ($2G$) is twice the gravitational constant (G), (c)² is the speed of light squared and (M) is the mass in kg, let's compare it with the formula (1.2) of cosmic velocity,

the (1.2)
$$(vc)^2 \cdot r = G \cdot M$$

with the (3.2)
$$r_s = \frac{2G}{c^2}M$$

We can also write the (3.2)
$$c^2 \cdot r_s = 2G \cdot M \quad (3.0.3)$$

Compared to the formula (1.2) of cosmic velocity (vc)² is replaced with (c)² the speed of light and the constant (G) it is double, it is obvious that with this formula we cannot calculate the cosmic velocity, as we have done in the previous chapters, but we will need it to calculate the deformation of space-time in relation to the cosmic velocity, practically with the formula (1.2) we calculate the cosmic velocity and with the formula (3.2) we calculate the maximum limit of the cosmic velocities. With the formula (1.2) we calculate a velocity with radiant action with respect to the center of gravity, with the formula (3.2) we calculate the limiting radius of each mass, which represents the event horizon of

black holes, from the combination of the formula of kinetic energy and potential energy, the result is the maximum velocity for the cosmic velocity vc .

Let's see how the radius varies (r) of the formula (1.2) from the radius (r_s), of formula (3.0.2) applying any value for the mass and for the radius, the result of (r_s) will always be 2 times the value(r) of the formula (1.2).

Let's rewrite the equation (3.0.3) $(c)^2 \cdot r_s = 2G \cdot M$

to match it (3.0.3) to the (1.2) $\frac{1}{2}(c)^2 \cdot r_s = G \cdot M$

which becomes, $0,5 \cdot (c)^2 \cdot r_s = G \cdot M$

which becomes, $((\sqrt{0,5} \cdot c)^2) \cdot r_s = G \cdot M$

and finally the formula for the limit speed, $(0,707 \cdot c)^2 \cdot r_s = G \cdot M$

we have adapted Newton's formula of universal gravitation with to the Schwarzschild radius formula, the definitive formula of the equation to apply it to the cosmic limiting velocity, becomes;

replacing in the (1.2) $(vc)^2$ with $(0.707 \cdot c)^2$

which becomes $(0.707 \cdot c)^2 \cdot r = G \cdot M$ (3.0.4)

With the new formula (3.0.4) we will also modify the divisor in the formula of special relativity (3.0.1), let's see the correct application in the formula (3.0.6).

With the formula of special relativity we calculate the dilation of time; in which Δt is the initial time and $\Delta t'$ is the resulting time, $(vc)^2$ is the cosmic velocity squared, $(c)^2$ is the speed of light squared. From the radius formula of Schwarzschild r_s we have seen that with respect to Newton's formula of gravitation, it involves us adapting the formula of special relativity on time, from the original formula as follows;

$$r_s = \frac{2G \cdot M}{c^2} \tag{3.0.2}$$

$$r_s = \frac{G \cdot M}{\frac{c^2}{2}} \tag{3.0.5}$$

Let's take the divisor of the (3.7) $\frac{c^2}{2}$ and we insert it into the (3.1),

We transform the divisor $\frac{(vc)^2}{c^2}$ in $\frac{(vc)^2}{\frac{c^2}{2}}$ which becomes $\frac{(vc)^2}{(V_{C-limit})^2}$ which become $\frac{(vc)^2}{(0.707 \cdot c)^2}$

The formula (3.0.1) $\Delta t = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)}} \Delta t'$

becomes $\Delta t = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v^2}{\frac{c^2}{2}}\right)}} \Delta t'$

The formula we need

$$\Delta t = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{(vc)^2}{(0.707 \cdot c)^2}\right)}} \Delta t' \quad (3.0.6)$$

(3.0.6) is the definitive formula we need to calculate the exact space-time deformation in relation to the upper limit of cosmic velocity.

(3.1.0) Application of the formula of special relativity with the limit of cosmic velocity

We check the variation in time caused by gravity, between the Earth's surface and the satellites for the GPS signal, which orbit at a distance of about 20 000 km¹ from the earth's surface. Let's take the velocity calculated on the earth's surface (2.0.3) $vc\ 1 = 7\ 908.66 \frac{m}{s}$ and velocity ($vc\ 2$) calculated at the distance of the satellites GPS (dsGPS), about 20 000 km¹ from the earth's surface. The official daily correction time for satellites for GPS instrument signals, due to the effect of time dilation caused by gravity, is currently 45μ¹ seconds a day late. Let's also take Karl Schwarzschild's formula, which calculated the exact solution of the equation of relativity of Einstein¹.

We have already calculated the average cosmic velocity on the Earth's surface, we call it $vc1$, Let's calculate the ones we need to define the deformation of time.

Cosmic speed on the Earth's surface $vc1 = 7\ 908.66$ (2.0.3)

We calculate the cosmic speed of the GPS satellite orbiting at a distance of 20 000 000 meters¹ from the earth's surface, we call it $vc2$, we set the formula; Mass of the Earth by Gravity Constant (G), divided by the sum of the mean radius of the earth (2.0.2) for the distance of the orbit of the GPS satellites.

Cosmic velocity on the satellite's orbit $GPS\ vc2 = \sqrt{\frac{G \cdot MT}{rT + (dsGPS)}}$ (3.1.1)

We enter the values into the formula, with the average radius of the Earth (2.0.2) (rT) is 6 371 km¹.

Cosmic Velocity Satellite $GPS\ vc2 = \sqrt{\frac{6.67259 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 5.972 \times 10^{24}}{(6\ 371\ 000 + 20\ 000\ 000)}} = 3\ 887.26 \frac{m}{s}$ (3.1.2)

Average cosmic velocity on the Earth's surface $vc1 = 7\ 908.66 \frac{m}{s}$ (2.0.3)

Satellite cosmic speed for GPS signal $vc2 = 3\ 887.26 \frac{m}{s}$ (3.1.2)

We set the cosmic velocities calculated with $vc1$ (2.0.3) and with $vc2$ (3.1.2) in the formula (3.0.6)

$$\text{Earth surface time } vc1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{(7\,908.66)^2}{(0.707 \cdot c)^2}\right)}} = 1.00000000069592 \text{ s} = 69.592 \times 10^{-11} \text{ s} \quad (3.1.3)$$

$$\text{GPS satellite time } vc2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{(3\,887.26)^2}{(0.707 \cdot c)^2}\right)}} = 1.00000000016813 \text{ s} = 16.681 \times 10^{-11} \text{ s} \quad (3.1.4)$$

We multiply the results by one day 86 400 seconds to calculate the dilation and consequent daily slowing down of time;

$$\text{Daily time slowdown } tvc1 = 69.959 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 86\,400 = 60,0128 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s} \quad (3.1.5)$$

$$\text{Daily time slowdown } tvc2 = 16.681 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 86\,400 = 14,4526 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s} \quad (3.1.6)$$

$$\text{Daily Time Difference} = 60.0128 \times 10^{-6} - 14.4526 \times 10^{-6} = 45,6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s} \quad (3.1.7)$$

The result (3.1.7) is compatible with the data calculated for the correction of $= 45,6 \mu\text{s}^{-1}$

We come to the conclusion that with the cosmic velocity, calculated with the formula (1.3) produced by a mass, we can calculate the space-time deformation with the formula of relativity, time lengthens and space shrinks, we can calculate the effects with Einstein's formula (3.0.1), corrected with the Schwarzschild radius formula, in formula (3.0.6).

From the formula setting, where the speed of light $(c.1)$ squared $(c)^2$ becomes $(0,707 \cdot c)^2$ It can be deduced that the cosmic speed can reach a maximum of 70.7% of the speed of light, let's make the relative calculation of the cosmic limit velocity.

$$V_{c-limit} = 0.707 \cdot c = 0.707 \cdot 299\,792\,458 = 211\,985\,280 \frac{m}{s} \quad (\text{Nc.4})$$

(3.2.0) Formula for Calculating Space-Time Deformation in Relation to Mass and Distance and Verification

We set the formula to calculate the deformation of space-time in relation to mass and distance, we rewrite the formula of cosmic velocity (1.3) and the formula (3.0.6).

We report the (1.3) $vc = \sqrt{\frac{G \cdot M}{r}}$ which we can also write by substituting the (r) of radius with the

$$\text{(d) of distance and leaving the cosmic velocity squared } (vc)^2 = \frac{G \cdot M}{d} \quad (3.2.1)$$

We also report the (3.0.6) $\Delta t = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{vc^2}{(0.707 \cdot c)^2}\right)}} \Delta t'$ and substitute in the divisor $\left(\frac{vc^2}{(0.707 \cdot c)^2}\right)$

the vc^2 with $\left(\frac{G \cdot M}{d}\right)$ and the formula (3.0.6) becomes $\Delta t = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{\left(\frac{G \cdot M}{d}\right)}{(0.707 \cdot c)^2}\right)}} \Delta t'$ (3.2.2)

(3.2.2) is the formula to calculate the space-time deformation relative to the distance with respect to the mass, let's make a check by calculating the time dilation on the earth's surface already performed in the calculation (3.1.3), enter the values the mass and the distance from the center of the earth.

Earth mass (2.0.1) = $5.972 \times 10^{24} \text{kg}$ Earth radius (2.0.2) = $6\,371\,000 \text{m}^1$

$$1\Delta t = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{\left(\frac{6.67259 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 5.972 \times 10^{24}}{6\,371\,000}\right)}{(0.707 \cdot c)^2}\right)}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{6.25470 \times 10^7}{4.49677 \times 10^{16}}\right)}} = 1.0000000006959 \Delta t'$$

The result is the same as (3.1.3) and confirms that the formula is valid.

(4.0.0) Formulas for calculating the size of black holes in relation to the density of mass, from Newton, Einstein to Schwarzschild

Let's summarize the calculations made in chapter 3.0, in formulas (3.0.4) and (3.0.6) we have replaced the value of $(vc)^2$ of formula (1.3) to find the cosmic velocity $\mathcal{V}C$, corrected in (3.0.4) for the Schwarzschild calculation, we have rewritten the formula of time dilation, of formula (1.3) by substituting $(vc)^2$ with $\frac{1}{2}(c)^2$ to calculate the maximum limit of cosmic velocity ($V_{c-limit}$).

The initial formula $(vc)^2 \cdot r = G \cdot M$ (1.2), has become the formula $\frac{1}{2}(c)^2 \cdot r = G \cdot M$ (4.0.1)

With the value of cosmic velocity $(V_{c-limit})^2$ replaced at the speed of light squared $(c)^2$ and the density of mass we can find the minimum limit of mass in kg, and the minimum length in meters of the radius of a spherical body, which by the effect of relativity, closes space at its periphery up to zero and lengthens time towards infinity. The celestial body becomes invisible, a black hole, we write the new equation. We also indicate the formula for the contraction of space.

The formula for the contraction of space, length $l = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)} l'$ (4.0.2)

with velocity (v) equal to the speed of light (C) the length (l) becomes zero.

To calculate the size of a black hole in relation to the density of its mass, we take the formula (4.0.1), in this formula we have two known values, $(c)^2$, The constant of the speed of light squared

and (G), the gravitational constant, we write the formula of the equation with two unknowns. From the observation of celestial bodies, it is assumed that the shape of black holes are spherical, so we need to find the radius (r) in meters of a sphere and the mass (M) in kg, depending on density ρ in $\frac{kg}{m^3}$ of the matter of which the black hole is presumed to be composed. We set the formulas for calculating the radius of the sphere, from the radius we obtain the volume, knowing that the mass is the product of the volume for the density ρ , we find the values we need.

Let's set the equation to two unknowns from (4.0.1).

$$\frac{1}{2}(c)^2 \cdot r = M \cdot G \begin{cases} \text{radius } r = \frac{m \cdot G}{\frac{1}{2}(c)^2} \\ \text{mass } M = \frac{\frac{1}{2}(c)^2 \cdot r}{G} \end{cases} \quad \begin{cases} r = \frac{m \cdot G}{\frac{1}{2}(c)^2} \\ \left[\left(\frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 \right) \cdot \rho \right] = \frac{\frac{1}{2}(c)^2 \cdot r}{G} \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} r = \frac{\{(4.188 \cdot r^3) \cdot \rho\} \cdot G}{\frac{1}{2}(c)^2} \\ (4.188 r^3) \cdot \rho = \frac{c^2 \cdot r}{2G} \end{cases} \quad \begin{cases} r = \frac{\{(4.188 \cdot r^3) \cdot \rho\} \cdot G}{\frac{1}{2}(c)^2} \\ \frac{r^3}{r} = \frac{c^2}{4.188 \cdot 2G \cdot \rho} \end{cases} \quad \begin{cases} r = \frac{\{(4.188 \cdot r^3) \cdot \rho\} \cdot G}{\frac{1}{2}(c)^2} \\ r^2 = \frac{c^2}{4.188 \cdot 2G \cdot \rho} \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} r = \frac{\{(4.188 \cdot r^3) \cdot \rho\} \cdot G}{\frac{1}{2}(c)^2} \\ r = \sqrt{\frac{c^2}{4.188 \cdot 2G \cdot \rho}} \end{cases} \quad \begin{cases} \text{radius } r = \sqrt{\frac{c^2}{4.188 \cdot 2G \cdot \rho}} \text{ meters} \\ \text{mass } M = \frac{4}{3} \pi \cdot \left(\sqrt{\frac{c^2}{4.188 \cdot 2G \cdot \rho}} \right)^3 \text{ kg} \end{cases} \quad \begin{matrix} (4.0.3) \\ (4.0.4) \end{matrix}$$

With the formulas (4.0.3) and (4.0.4) elaborated above, we can calculate and the radius (r) and the mass (M) of an agglomeration of matter with a spherical shape, which based on its density has such a force of gravity, that at the surface of the agglomeration a cosmic limit velocity of 70.7% of the speed of light ($Nc.4$) is produced as obtained from the formula (3.0.6), with the cosmic velocity at this limit, time should lengthen towards infinity and space close towards zero, For the final calculation we only need to set a density ρ to the material of the agglomeration.

(4.1.0) Calculations of black holes, in relation to the density of mass

Let's take an example: let's calculate the size of a black hole, with the density of our star the Sun, equal to $\rho 1410 \frac{kg}{m^3}$, We calculate the size of the black hole, start to derive the radius of the agglomerate sphere, put the density into the formula ρ (4.0.3).

$$\text{Black Hole Radius} = \sqrt{\frac{c^2}{4.188 \cdot 2G \cdot 1410}} = 3.37679 \times 10^{11} \text{ metri} \quad (4.1.1)$$

The result (4.1.1) is an object with a radius, almost equal in size to the distance between Earth and Mars, i.e. = 3.6×10^{11} meters¹, only totally invisible due to the fact that the space on its periphery is totally closed.

Once the radius in meters of the black hole sphere has been found, to find the mass, just multiply the density ρ by the volume of the sphere, $\frac{4}{3}\pi \cdot r^3$; knowing the radius (r) 4.1.1).

Here is the formula for the volume V and the mass M of the sphere $V = \frac{4}{3}\pi \cdot r^3$, $M = V \cdot \rho$

$$\text{mass } M = \frac{4}{3}\pi \cdot (3.37679 \times 10^{11} \text{ meters})^3 \cdot \rho (1410 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}) = 2.2741 \times 10^{38} \text{ kg} \quad (4.1.3)$$

the result (4.1.3) is about 114 million times the mass of the Sun.

Having obtained the mass (4.1.3) of the black hole, we verify by finding the radius of the mass with the Schwarzschild formula r_s (3.2).

$$r_s = \frac{2G \cdot M}{c^2} = \frac{2 \cdot 6.67259 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 2.27416 \times 10^{38}}{(299\,792\,458)^2} = 3.37679 \times 10^{11} \text{ meters}$$

The result is the same as (4.1.1) is the demonstration that the calculation is correct.

Let's do the verification by calculating the cosmic velocity at the periphery of the black hole with the mass of (4.1.3), take the data calculated above and set the equation with the formula (1.3).

$$\text{i.e. } v_c = \sqrt{\frac{\text{Black Hole mass} \cdot G}{\text{Black Hole radius}}} = \sqrt{\frac{2.27416 \times 10^{38} \cdot 6.67259 \times 10^{-11}}{3.37679 \times 10^{11}}} = 211\,985\,280 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}} \quad (4.1.4)$$

the verification confirms that the result of (4.1.4) coincides with the constant (Nc.4) and confirms that at the periphery of a black hole the cosmic limit velocity is 70.7% of the speed of light.

Knowing the cosmic limiting velocity and radius, we also calculate with (1.4) the gravitational acceleration on the surface of the event horizon of the black hole with the density of the Sun.

$$\text{Acceleration Force } g = \frac{(v_c \text{ limite})^2}{r_{\text{raggio buco nero}}} = \frac{(211\,985\,280)^2}{3.37679 \times 10^{11}} = 133\,078,16 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}^2} \quad (4.1.5)$$

Let's see how much the gravitational acceleration of the black hole has increased with respect to the current Sun, let's start calculating the cosmic speed first, set up the calculation, knowing the mass and radius of the Sun, enter them into the formula (1.3).

$$v_c = \sqrt{\frac{\text{Sun mass} \cdot G}{\text{Sun radius}}} = \sqrt{\frac{1.989 \times 10^{30} \cdot 6.67259 \times 10^{-11}}{696\,340\,000}} = 436\,570 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}} \quad (4.1.6)$$

Having found the cosmic velocity, let's calculate the gravitational acceleration of (4.1.6) with (1.4)

$$\text{Acceleration force on the surface of the Sun } g = \frac{(436\,570)^2}{696\,340\,000} = 273.70 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}^2} \quad (4.1.7)$$

Recall that the acceleration force (g) on the Earth's surface is 9.81 Newton (2.0.4)

In the calculations of some supermassive black holes, the acceleration exceeds the speed of light, the result is compatible because the acceleration can exceed the speed of light, the acceleration has no limit.

We see the size of the black hole when the density changes ρ ,

Let's do the calculation with the heaviest element we know of on Earth, the chemical element Osmium (Os) with a density of $22\,590 \frac{kg}{m^3}$ by doing the calculations, the respective results are,

Black Hole Radius $r = 2.667 \times 10^{10}$ meters, Black Hole mass $M = 1.796 \times 10^{37}$ kg.

The size is less than half the distance between the Sun and Mercury, $= 6.9 \times 10^{10}$ meters¹, the mass is less than 10 million times the mass of the Sun.

We calculate a black hole with the density of the subatomic particle, the neutron with density equal to $2,0 \times 10^{17} \frac{kg}{m^3}$ the dimensions result, respectively, for the radius of the black hole = 28 353 meters, and the mass $M = 1.90945 \times 10^{31}$ kg.

It would measure a diameter of only 28.35 km and would have a mass of about 10 times the mass of the Sun.

We calculate the gravitational acceleration for a black hole with the density of the neutron, knowing that the cosmic limiting velocity is equal to $211\,985\,280 \frac{m}{s}$.

$$g \text{ force for Black Hole with Neutron Density } g = \frac{(211\,985\,280)^2}{28\,353} = 1.5849 \times 10^{12} \frac{m}{s^2} \quad (4.1.8)$$

In (4.1.8) the acceleration exceeds the speed of light, the result of the calculation is compatible.

For the lightest element we know, hydrogen with ρ equal to $0.0899 \frac{kg}{m^3}$ since hydrogen is a gas, we must imagine it in an ideal situation, crystallized and incompressible, the dimensions are for,

$$\text{The radius of the hydrogen black hole} = 4.229 \times 10^{13} \text{ metri,} \quad (4.1.9)$$

$$\text{The mass of the hydrogen black hole} = 2.848 \times 10^{40} \text{ kg.} \quad (4.1.10)$$

It would be about 7.1 times the distance between the Sun and Pluto 5.9×10^{12} meters¹, and a mass of about 14 billion times the mass of the Sun, in conclusion, black holes composed of matter with densities of known elements are 10 to 100 million times the size of the Sun, while for a black hole of the density of the subatomic particle the Neutron is about 15 times the mass of the Sun, while for hydrogen it turns out to be 14 billion times larger.

(5.0.0) The quantum mass M_q

Let's move on to the heart of this work; The theory of the quantum expansion of space with the hypothesis of the action of dark matter, this new theory hypothesizes that empty space expands at every point, with constant speed and time, that empty space contains a ponderable amount of matter, which slowly converts into energy at a quantum rate.

Let's assume that it is dark matter, distributed in a homogeneous way, at an infinitesimal level throughout space even in subatomic space, it is hypothesized that this matter has its own mass, calculable in Kg and its energy measurable in joules.

We know that dark matter, calculated in the observed celestial phenomena, does not absorb electromagnetic waves and for these reasons it still remains invisible to current instruments. Let's try to find a trace of this matter, looking for a value similar to the value of Planck's quanta (h), a packet of matter expressed in kg, similar to quanta expressed in joules.

Discovered by the German physicist Max Planck, he gave him the name of quanta and from this discovery quantum physics began, he showed that energy is divided into discrete quantities of unit packets, these packets of energy reach a limit point where its value is no longer divisible, and all the energy we calculate is a multiple value of these discrete packets of energy¹.

With this premise, since the topics we have discussed, gravity and cosmic velocity are totally dependent on mass, let's look for a value for an infinitesimal point of matter, which we will call quantum mass, to which we assign the symbol M_q .

the value of Planck's constant $h = 6.626 \times 10^{-34}$ joules · seconds , (c.3)

practically a joule and composed of $\frac{1 \text{ joule}}{6.626 \times 10^{-34}} = 1.509 \times 10^{33}$ quanta (energy packets)

Verification; $6.626 \times 10^{-34} \cdot 1.509 \times 10^{33} = 1 \text{ joule}$

Quantum mass M_q that we are looking for is a ponderable entity, expressible with its weight in kg, to calculate its value we need Planck's constant (h) and convert it into quanta of mass, we use Einstein's formula, in which he demonstrates the relationship between masses and energy $E = M \cdot C^2$, for our purpose we take Planck's constant and insert it into Einstein's formula, substituting E with h , from the result we derive the value of a particle of mass for each quantum of energy, we set up the calculation, we take Einstein's formula, the formula expresses that the energy (E) is equal to the mass (M) for the speed of light squared (c)².

$$\text{Einstein's classical formula } E = M \cdot c^2 \quad (5.0.1)$$

$$\text{We replace } E \text{ with } h \quad h = M \cdot c^2$$

$$\text{We insert } M_q \text{ instead of } M \quad h = M_q \cdot c^2$$

$$\text{quantum mass } M_q = \frac{h}{c^2} \quad (5.0.2)$$

$$\text{value of quantum mass } M_q = \frac{h}{c^2} = \frac{6.626 \times 10^{-34}}{(299\,792\,458)^2} = 7.3725033 \times 10^{-51} \text{kg} \quad (5.0.3)$$

With the result (5.0.3) we calculated a mass for each quantum of energy and we gave it a value in kg, it is a new value, we assign it the name of quantum mass and the symbol M_q we will indicate with the number (Nc.1).

Let's assume that dark matter and dark energy have a relationship with quantum mass, let's see the physical characteristics of quantum mass.

(5.1.0) The physical characteristics of quantum mass M_q

Let's calculate the physical characteristics of quantum mass M_q . By processing the results with the formulas of atomic physics used for photons, we identify the energy E , the Frequency f , and the Wavelength λ ,

The formulas are:

$$\text{For energy } E \text{ of a mass } M ; \quad E = M \cdot c^2 \quad (5.1.1)$$

$$\text{For the mass } M \text{ of a photon frequency } f ; \quad M = \frac{h \cdot f}{c^2} \quad (5.1.2)$$

$$\text{For the frequency of a mass photon } M ; \quad f = \frac{M \cdot c^2}{h} \quad (5.1.3)$$

$$\text{for the wavelength of a photon } \lambda ; \quad \lambda = \frac{h}{M \cdot c} \quad (5.1.4)$$

Having calculated quantum mass M_q (Nc1) = $7.3725033 \times 10^{-51}$ kg and knowing the energy equal to one quantum of Planck's constant (c.3) $h = 6.626 \times 10^{-34}$ joules · seconds and knowing the constant of the speed of light (c.1) $c = 299\,792\,458$ meters/seconds;

We calculate the energy E of the mass M_q (5.1.1);

$$E = 7.3725033 \times 10^{-51} \cdot (299\,792\,458)^2 = 6.626 \times 10^{-3} \text{ joule} \quad (5.1.5)$$

Let's calculate the other values, let's start with the frequency of a mass photon M_q (5.1.3) f ;

$$f = \frac{M_q \cdot c^2}{h} = \frac{7.3725033 \times 10^{-51} \cdot (299\,792\,458)^2}{6.626 \times 10^{-34}} = 1 \text{ Hz} \quad (5.1.6)$$

Frequency found f We calculate the wavelength for a mass photon M_q (5.1.4) λ ;

$$\lambda = \frac{h}{M_q \cdot c} = \frac{6.626 \times 10^{-34}}{7.3725033 \times 10^{-51} \cdot 299\,792\,458} = 299\,792\,458 \text{ meters} \quad (5.1.7)$$

Finally, let's check the frequency for an electromagnetic wave f ,

$$\text{Frequency of an electromagnetic wave } f = \frac{c}{\lambda} = \frac{299\,792\,458}{299\,792\,458} = 1 \quad (5.1.8)$$

considered as a photon; Frequency $f = 1$ Herz Wavelength $\lambda = 299\,792\,458$ meters

(6.0) Introduction to general relativity and the Field equation

Einstein's field equation is the fundamental equation of the theory of general relativity. It describes the curvature of space-time as a function of the density of matter, energy and pressure, with which all astronomical phenomena can be calculated with exactitude¹.

Field Equation Formula
$$G_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu} \quad (6.1)$$

In the formula (6.1) the cosmological constant with the symbol Λ ¹ is missing, we report the formula of the complete equation in (6.2) the cosmological constant refers in general to an energy component capable of integrating the cosmological model deriving from general relativity¹. The first term cosmological constant was the term added by Albert Einstein in 1917 in the field equation of general relativity¹ to obtain a model of a static universe¹, implying a dynamical universe¹. Practically it is a repulsive force opposed to gravity, it was introduced to prevent the force of gravity from collapsing the universe on itself¹. After Hubble discovered the expansion of the universe's space, Einstein eliminated it from the formula by calling it "His biggest mistake"¹.

In this work we calculate a value that we call a cosmological constant and assign it the symbol Λ , which has in common with the field equation¹ only the numerical value of the Ricci scalar, practically the value we will calculate cannot be used in the formula of the field equation, it is simply a constant that multiplied by the distance indicates a velocity as a result.

Let's break down the formula of the field equation, with Einstein's cosmological constant Λ . We only need the value of the part of the Ricci scalar formula (6.5).

Original Field Equation Formula
$$G_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu} \quad (6.2)$$

The original formula (6.2) is divided into four parts:

First part $G_{\mu\nu}$ = Einstein tensor, (6.3)

(6.3) represents the geometry (curvature) of spacetime.

Second part $\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}$ = cosmological constant (6.4)

In (6.4) where $\Lambda = \frac{8\pi G}{c^2} \rho_{vac}$ has the value of approximately 10^{-120}

Third part $\frac{8\pi G}{c^4}$ = Ricci scalar, numerical part, constants and pi (6.5)

Part Four $T_{\mu\nu}$ = Energy-impulse tensor, (6.6)

(6.6) represents the distribution of matter and energy.

(7.0.0) The quantum cosmological constant Λ_q

We calculate the quantum cosmological constant, we integrate the formula by inserting the quantum mass M_q (Nc1) with the formula of cosmic velocity (1.2) in the part of the formula with which Einstein calculated his cosmological constant (6.4), the one with Ricci's scalar (6.5). Let's start by substituting (M) the formula (1.2) with quantum mass M_q ;

The formula (1.2)
$$(vc)^2 \cdot r = G \cdot M$$

becomes
$$[(vc)^2 \cdot r] = (G \cdot M_q)$$

$$[(vc)^2 \cdot r] = (6.67259 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 7,37250 \times 10^{-5}) \quad (7.0.1)$$

The cosmic velocity squared for the radius is equal to the quantum mass M_q for the gravitational constant (G), The next step will be to enter the formula (7.0.1) of the cosmic velocity with quantum mass, we take the constant Λ of the cosmological constant (6.4) and we replace it with the matter-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ and we replace the space-time tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ with $G \cdot M_q$

We rewrite the modified formula, knowing that
$$M_q = \frac{h}{c^2}$$

The equation becomes:
$$\Lambda_q \cdot \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} = G \cdot \frac{h}{c^2}$$

We simplify,
$$\Lambda_q = \frac{G \cdot \frac{h}{c^2}}{\frac{8\pi G}{c^4}}$$

which becomes,
$$\Lambda_q = \frac{G \cdot \frac{h}{c^2} \cdot c^4}{8\pi G}$$

The definitive formula for the constant
$$\Lambda_q = \frac{h \cdot c^2}{8\pi} \quad (7.0.2)$$

We can observe that in the final formula the constant (G) disappears completely.

Let's complete the formula by making the size corrections, leaving out 8π because it is devoid of dimensions.

$$\frac{h = \text{jou} \cdot \text{seconds} \cdot c^2 = \left(\frac{\text{meters}}{\text{seconds}}\right)^2}{8\pi} = (N \cdot m \cdot S) \cdot \frac{m^2}{s^2} = \left(\frac{kg \cdot m^2}{s^2} \cdot S\right) \cdot \frac{m^2}{s^2} = \frac{kg \cdot m^4}{s^3}$$

We transform the dimensions of the (7.0.2) to make it become a speed in m/s.

The dimensions of the (7.0.2)
$$\frac{kg \cdot m^4}{s^3} \cdot \frac{s^2}{kg \cdot m^3} = \frac{m}{s} ;$$

become;

$$\Lambda q = \frac{h \cdot c^2}{8\pi} \cdot \frac{s^2}{kg \cdot m^3} = \frac{m}{s}$$

The ultimate formula with dimensions $\Lambda q = \frac{h \cdot c^2}{8\pi} \cdot \frac{m}{s}$ (7.0.3)

Now that we have the formula, let's enter the values of the constants into the equation (7.0.3):

$$\Lambda q = \frac{6.626 \times 10^{-34} \cdot (299\,792\,458)^2}{8 \cdot 3.1459} = 2.3695066 \times 10^{-18} \frac{m}{s} \quad (7.0.4)$$

$$\Lambda q = 2.3695066 \times 10^{-18} \frac{m}{s} \quad (Nc.2)$$

We calculate the constant by directly dividing the product of the gravitational constant by the quantum mass ($G \cdot M_q$) (7.0.1) with the numerical result of the Ricci scalar (c11);

let's take up the numerical result in the Ricci scalar to which we have assigned the number (c11);

$$\text{value of the Ricci scalar} = \frac{8\pi}{c^4} = \frac{8 \cdot (3.14) \cdot 6.67259 \times 10^{-11}}{(299\,792\,458)^4} = 2.076115 \times 10^{-43} \quad (c.11)$$

$$\text{Direct calculation of the constant } \Lambda q = \frac{G \cdot M_q}{\frac{8\pi G}{c^4}} \quad (7.0.5)$$

$$\Lambda q = \frac{6.67259 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 7.3725033 \times 10^{-51}}{2.076115 \times 10^{-43}}$$

$$\Lambda q = \frac{4.919369 \times 10^{-6}}{2.076115 \times 10^{-4}} = 2.3695066 \times 10^{-1} \frac{m}{s} \quad (Nc.2)$$

Also in formulas (7.0.5) as in (7.0.3) the gravitational constant G is cancelled, given the variability of the measurement of the constant the result should be more precise.

The "Quantum Cosmological Constant" is a rate of expansion of the volume of a sphere of empty space that has a radius of one meter, which expands by $2.3695066 \times 10^{-18}$ meters per second.

The result of (7.05) and (7.03) is a new constant, we have assigned it the symbol Λq lambda Λ followed by a (q) for quantum and the number (Nc.2). As we will see in the following chapters, the result of the expansion of space is also calculated with the formula of cosmic velocity (1.3).

(7.1.0) The rate of expansion of space between the Earth and the Moon with the cosmological constant and verification

We apply the new cosmological constant (Nc2) to calculate the expansion of the interplanetary vacuum between the Earth and the Moon, from the measurements we know that the Moon moves away from the Earth at a speed of approximately, between 2.8 cm^1 and 3.8 cm^1 annual. We know that the Moon orbits the Earth in an elliptical way, let's take the cosmological constant (Nc2) and we apply

it to the various distances of the orbit, the maximum distance is 405 000 000 meters¹ and the minimum distance is 360 000 000 meters¹ and for the average distance which by convention is 384 400 000 meters¹, multiply the distance between the Earth and the Moon by the quantum cosmological constant Λ_q .

At the maximum distance equal to 405 000 000 meters¹

$$405\,000\,000 \cdot 2.3695066 \times 10^{-18} = 9.5965 \times 10^{-10} \text{ meters /seconds}$$

$$= 0.03026 \text{ meters /year} = 3.026 \text{ centimeters/year} \quad (7.1.1)$$

At the average distance equal to 384.400.000 meters¹

$$384\,400\,000 \cdot 2.3695066 \times 10^{-18} = 9.10838 \times 10^{-10} \text{ meters/seconds}$$

$$= 0.02872 \text{ meters/year} = 2.872 \text{ centimeters/year} \quad (7.1.2)$$

At the minimum distance equal to 360 000 000 meters

$$360\,000\,000 \cdot 2.3695066 \times 10^{-18} = 8.5302 \times 10^{-10} \text{ meters/seconds}$$

$$= 0.02690 \text{ meters/year} = 2.690 \text{ centimeters/year} \quad (7.1.3)$$

All results are compatible with the estimated measurements, in chapter (8.1) we verify with the cosmic velocity formula (1.3).

(7.2.0) The rate of expansion of space over the distance of one mega parsec (Mpc) with the cosmological constant and verification

We calculate the expansion of the vacuum for the distance of a mega parsec, a parsec corresponds to the distance of 3.262 Light years¹ one mega parsec (Mpc) corresponds to the distance of one million parsecs equal to 3 262 000 Light years¹ is the distance at which the cosmic rate of expansion is calculated with the Hubble constant¹ (c8) which has the symbol H_0 ¹ as already mentioned in the previous chapters, it is calculated with different methods that leads to divergent velocity values, we can say that the reference result is between 67.4 and 76.5 km¹ per second for mega parsec (Mpc).

We convert parsecs (SI Units) to meters = 3.0857×10^{16} meters¹ in mega parsecs, to find the new Hubble constant H_0 with the value of the cosmological constant (Nc2).

$$\Lambda_q \cdot 1 \text{ Mpc} = (\Lambda_q \cdot 1 \text{ parsec} \cdot 1 \text{ milion}) = (2.369506 \times 10^{-18} \cdot 3.0856776 \times 10^{16} \cdot (1 \cdot 10)^6) =$$

$$\Lambda_q \cdot 1 \text{ Mpc} = 73\,115.335 \text{ meters per second for mega parsec} \quad (\text{Nc.3}) \quad (7.2.1)$$

The result (7.2.1) is a value for the Hubble constant that we call the "quantum Hubble constant" and assign it the symbol H_q (Nc.3) its value is 73 115.335 m/s for mega parsec.

The speed of the constant (Nc.3) falls between the 67 400 m/s¹ and 76 500 m/s¹ therefore we consider it compatible with the measurements observed.

(7.3.0) The rate of expansion of interatomic space of the volume of the Earth and the likely effects observed on the Earth's surface.

As we wrote in the introduction, it is theorized that dark matter is found everywhere in space and therefore the expansion of the vacuum occurs in all points of space, even in subatomic space.

We calculate the volumetric dimensions of the Earth's void, without taking into account the mass of matter, as if the volume of the Earth were a bubble of empty space. We report the known values;

$$\text{Earth's average radius } rT = 6\,371\,000 \text{ m}^1 \quad (2.3)$$

$$\text{Quantum cosmological constant } \Lambda q = 2.369506 \times 10^{-11} \frac{m}{s} \quad (\text{Nc.2})$$

To calculate the expansion we use the simplest formula, mean radius of the earth rT for the quantum cosmological constant Λq (Nc.2), let's set the calculation;

$$\text{Expansion Void Ground; } \Lambda q \cdot rT = 2.3695066 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 6\,371\,000^1 = 1.509 \times 10^{-11} \frac{m}{s} \quad (7.3.1)$$

The space of the Earth's radius should expand by 1.509×10^{-11} meters per second, with the result we calculate the effect on the circumference of the Earth, formula circumference = $2\pi r$, expansion per second of the Earth's circumference.

$$\text{Earth circumverence} = (2 \cdot 3.14159) \cdot 1.509 \times 10^{-11} = 9.4851 \times 10^{-11} \frac{m}{s} \quad (7.3.2)$$

To calculate the annual expansion, we multiply seconds by years

$$\text{per year according to} = 9.4851 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 31\,0536\,000 = 2.9912 \times 10^{-3} \frac{m}{\text{annual}} \quad (7.3.3)$$

The result (7.3.3) is about 3 millimeters per year, let's see if it is compatible with continental drift,

Let's measure the distance of two tectonic plates, that of South America ¹, specifically the Brazilian coast¹, and that of Central Africa¹, the distance is about 2 840 km¹, let's see how long it should have taken, with the calculated expansion of 3 millimeters per year, let's set the formula by making the average expansion of the circumference, since the continents were united, and to the current circumference. Circumference of the earth at the present equator 40 075 km¹ minus the present distance of the continents 2 840 km¹ the starting circumference was 37 235 km.

$$\text{Initial expansion } 37\,235\,000 \cdot 2.3695066 \times 10^{-18} = 8.82228 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 31\,536\,000 = 2.78 \times 10^{-3} \frac{m}{\text{annual}}$$

$$\text{Medium Expansion} = 2.7824 \times 10^{-3} + 2.9912 \times 10^{-3} = 5.777 \times 10^{-3} = \frac{5.777 \times 10^{-3}}{2} = 2.888 \times 10^{-3} \frac{m}{\text{annual}}$$

With the average expansion we calculate the hypothetical time it took to expand,

$$\text{Time} = \frac{\text{plates distance}}{\text{medium annual expansions}} = \frac{2\,840\,000}{0.002888} = 983\,214\,171 \text{ years} \quad (7.3.4)$$

The time for continental drift between the South American and African plates, calculated with the cosmological constant, is about 983 million years, the time indicated by geologists is about 200 million years ¹, 20 % of the expansion could depend on the expansion of the subatomic vacuum.

(7.4.0) The speed of expansion of the space between the Milky Way and Andromeda galaxies

Let's calculate the escape velocity between our Milky Way galaxy and the Andromeda galaxy, we just need to recover the distance in meters that we calculated in the chapter (2.3.0),

distance $2,40138 \cdot 10^{22}$ meters (2.4.1), multiply the distance by the cosmological constant Λq

$$\Lambda q \cdot \text{galaxy distance} = 2.369506 \times 10^{-18} \cdot 2.40138 \times 10^{22} = 56\,900.88 \frac{m}{s} \quad (7.4.1)$$

Having calculated the speed of approach of the two galaxies with the cosmic velocity, we subtract the speed of expansion and find an estimated speed of approach. From the sum of the two cosmic velocities (2.3.9) we subtract the escape velocity (7.4.1)

$$\text{Estimated Approach Speed} = 119\,554.29 - 56\,900.88 = 62\,653.42 \frac{m}{s} \quad (7.4.2)$$

The result of (7.4.2) shows that the approach speed of the two galaxies should be approximately 63 km/s. About half the estimated speed between the 100 km/s and 140 km/s¹.

(7.5.0) The expansion of the space of the observable universe with the cosmological constant and verification

Let's make the calculations considering that the speed of the expansion of the universe can reach the speed of light, that is, the cosmic speed that equals that of light. In chapter 7.0, we calculated that the universe expands at the speed of 73 115 meters/seconds per mega parsec, now we need to calculate the number of resulting mega parsecs for which the cosmic speed equals the speed of light, just divide the speed of light (c.1) by the new Hubble constant H_q (Nc.3)

Calculating the number of mega parsecs needed to equal cosmic speed to the speed of light;

$$\text{Mega parsec distance} \frac{\text{speed of light}}{\text{Hubble constant}} = \frac{c}{H_q} = \frac{299\,792\,458}{73\,115.335} = 4\,100.268 \text{ mega parsec} \quad (7.5.1)$$

To find the radius of the universe visible in meters, simply multiply the number of mega parsecs by the distance in meters per mega parsec (c.12)

$$\text{Visible universe radius} = 4\,100.268 \cdot 3.0856776 \times 10^{22} = 1.26521 \times 10^{26} \text{ metri}$$

$$\text{Or} \frac{\text{speed of light}}{\text{cosmological constant}} = \frac{c}{\Lambda q} = \frac{299\,792\,458}{2.369506 \times 10^{-18}} = 1,26521 \times 10^{26} \text{ meters} \quad (7.5.2)$$

We convert the radius of the universe visible from meters to light years,

$$1 \text{ Light Year} = 9.461 \times 10^{15} \text{ meters}^1 \quad (c.10)$$

$$\text{We calculate} \frac{1.26521 \times 10^{26}}{9,461 \times 10^{15}} = 1.338 \times 10^{10} \text{ years} = 13.38 \text{ billions of light years,} \quad (7.5.3)$$

The distance calculated with (7.5.3) is close to the age of the universe estimated to be between 13.5 and 13.8 billion light-years¹.

Having found the length of the radius of the visible universe in meters, we verify the speed of expansion, multiplying the length of the radius (7.5.2) for the cosmological constant Λq (Nc.2).

$$\text{Check: Speed } \Lambda q = 1.26521 \times 10^{26} \cdot 2.369506 \times 10^{-18} = 299\,792\,458 \text{ meters/seconds} \quad (7.5.4)$$

As expected, the result (7.5.4) is equal to the constant of the speed of light (c.1).

(8.0.0) Calculation of the density, mass and energy of dark matter contained in one cubic meter of empty space

We calculate the density in kg, the energy in joules, of the dark matter contained in one cubic meter of empty space, we make use of the new quantum expansion constant Λq , we insert instead of cosmic velocity in the formula (1.2), $(vc)^2 \cdot r = G \cdot M$ we replace $(vc)^2$ with $(\Lambda q)^2$

$$(\Lambda q)^2 \cdot r = G \cdot M, \text{ the formula for mass is, } M = \frac{(\Lambda q)^2 \cdot r}{G}, \text{ with radius } (r) = 1 \text{ meter}$$

$$\text{mass } M = \frac{(2.369506 \times 10^{-18})^2 \cdot 1}{6.67259 \times 10^{-11}} = 8.41437 \times 10^{-26} \text{ kg} \quad (8.0.1)$$

The result of the calculation (8.0.1) is valid for a sphere with a radius of 1 meter, equivalent to a volume of 4.188 m^3 , to find the density ρ by cubic meters we divide by $\frac{4}{3}\pi = 4.188$ let's do the calculation,

$$\text{Dark matter density } \rho \zeta = \frac{8.41437 \times 10^{-26} \text{ kg}}{4.188 \text{ m}^3} = 2.008781976 \times 10^{-26} \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}, \quad (\text{Nc.5}) \quad (8.0.2)$$

The result (8.0.2) is the density of dark matter contained in one cubic meter of empty space, it is a new value, we assign it the number (Nc.5) and the symbol ($\rho \zeta$), we will use it to calculate the cosmic velocity with the formulas (1.3). With the value of density we can calculate the energy in joules of dark matter (8.0.2) of a cubic meter of space, we use Einstein's formula $E = M \cdot c^2$

$$\text{Energy in joule } E \zeta = 2,008781976 \times 10^{-26} \cdot c^2 = 1,8054 \times 10^{-9} \text{ joule } \text{m}^3, \quad (\text{Nc.6}) \quad (8.0.3)$$

with (8.0.3) we have found the energy of dark matter contained in a cubic meter of empty space is a new value and we assign it the number (Nc.6) and the symbol ($E \zeta$).

(8.1.0) Calculation of the expansion of the space between the Earth and the Moon with the density of dark matter contained in the vacuum and verification

In the previous chapter we calculated the density of dark matter contained in a cubic meter of vacuum, now we calculate, with the formulas of cosmic velocity (1.3), the rate of expansion of the

vacuum between the Earth and the Moon, to begin we calculate the volume of the vacuum, and we insert the density into the volume of space of the formula (1.3).

the volume in m^3 and mass in kg with the average distance, by 384 000 000 m^1

$$\text{volume of the Earth-Moon void} = \left(\frac{4}{3} \pi \cdot (384\,000\,000)^3 \right) = 2.37924 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}^3, \quad (8.1.1)$$

calculated the volume (8.1.1) knowing the density of dark matter ρ_{ζ} (Nc5), Let's calculate the mass in kg of dark matter;

$$\text{Earth-Moon vacuum mass} = 2.37924 \times 10^{-26} \cdot 2.008781976 \times 10^{26} = 4.77938 \text{ kg}, \quad (8.1.2)$$

Knowing the radius and mass, we calculate the speed of expansion of space at the distance of the average orbit of the Moon with the formula (1.3),

$$(\text{expansion velocity})^2 \cdot r = \sqrt{\frac{G \cdot \text{void mass (kg)}}{\text{Earth - Moon distance (m)}}}$$

$$\text{Expansion per second} = \sqrt{\frac{6.67259 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 4.77938}{384\,400\,000}} = 9.10838 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m/s} \quad (8.1.3)$$

In addition to the known data, we need the seconds contained in a year, we take (c.9) and calculate when it expands in a year, multiply (8.1.3) by seconds per year.

$$\text{Expansion per year} = 9.10838 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m/s} \cdot 31\,536\,000 \text{ s} = 0.02872 \text{ m} \quad (8.1.4)$$

The result of the calculation (8.1.4) corresponding to cm year = 2,872 cm, fits perfectly with the result of the calculation (7.1.2) made with the quantum cosmological constant (Nc.2).

(8.2.0) Calculation of the expansion of space of the distance of a mega parsec with the density of dark matter contained in the vacuum and verification

Let's calculate the expansion rate of space of the distance of a mega parsec, as in the previous chapter we need the volume of a mega parsec to calculate the mass.

$$1 \text{ Mega parsec} = 3.0856776 \times 10^{22} \text{ metri} \quad (c.12)$$

Knowing the radius we find the volume of space of a mega parsec

$$\text{Space volume of a mega parsec} = \frac{4}{3} \pi \cdot (3.0856776 \times 10^{22})^3 = 1.23067 \times 10^{68} \text{ m}^3, \quad (8.2.1)$$

As in the previous chapter, multiply the volume of the vacuum by the density of dark matter ρ_{ζ} ,

$$\text{Vacuum mass of a Mpc} = 1.23067 \times 10^{68} \cdot 2.008781976 \times 10^{-26} = 2.47214 \times 10^{42} \text{ kg} \quad (8.2.2)$$

Knowing the distance r in meters and the mass M in kg, we calculate the new Hubble constant H_0 for Mpc, let's apply the formula $(H_0)^2 \cdot r = M \cdot G$,

$$\text{Hubble constant } (H_o) = \sqrt{\frac{6.67259 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 2.47214 \times 10^{42}}{3.0856776 \times 10^{22}}} = 73 \text{ 115.335 m/s} \cdot \text{megaparsec} \quad (8.2.3)$$

Also the calculation (8.2.3) fits perfectly with the result of the calculation (7.2.1), the result is the constant (Nc.3)

(8.3.0) The expansion of the space between the Milky Way and Andromeda galaxies with the density of dark matter contained in the vacuum and verifies

As in the previous chapters we need to derive the volume of space, for this reason we report the distance of the galaxies that we have already calculated in (2.4.1) which represents the radius of the volume of the sphere, distance = Radius = 2.40138×10^{22} metri.

$$\text{Volume space between galaxies} = \frac{4}{3} \pi \cdot (2.40138 \times 10^{22})^3 = 5.8005836 \times 10^{67} \text{ m}^3, \quad (8.3.1)$$

To calculate the weight of the vacuum, simply multiply the volume of the vacuum by the density of the vacuum's dark matter.

$$\text{Vacuum mass} = 5.800536 \times 10^{67} \cdot 2.008781976 \times 10^{-26} = 1.16521 \times 10^{42} \text{ kg} \quad (8.3.2)$$

Knowing the distance (r) in meters and the mass (M) in kg, we calculate the escape velocity of galaxies we apply the formula $(\text{escape velocity})^2 \cdot r = M \cdot G$,

$$\text{escape velocity} = \sqrt{\frac{6.67259 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 1.16521 \times 10^{42}}{2.40138 \times 10^{22}}} = 56 \text{ 900.88 m/s} \quad (8.3.3)$$

The result of the calculation (8.3.3) fits perfectly with the result of the cosmic velocity (7.4.1)

(8.4.0) The expansion of the space of the observable universe with the density of dark matter contained in the vacuum and verifies

We report the radius of the universe that we have already calculated in the (8.4.2) to calculate the volume.

$$\text{Volume Universe} = \frac{4}{3} \pi \cdot (1.2651 \times 10^{26})^3 = 8.483536 \times 10^{78} \text{ m}^3 \quad (8.4.1)$$

From the volume (8.5.1) we calculate the mass, knowing the density of the dark matter of the vacuum (Nc.5)

$$\text{The mass of the vacuum} = 8.483536 \times 10^{78} \cdot 2.008781976 \times 10^{-26} = 1.704157 \times 10^{53} \text{ kg} \quad (8.4.2)$$

The result of the mass (8.4.2) of dark matter is almost twice the baryonic mass of the visible matter of the universe, calculated to be approximately on the 10^{53} kg^1 ,

once the mass has been found, we verify with the formula (1.3) to find the cosmic velocity,

$$vc = \sqrt{\frac{G \cdot \text{universe mass}}{\text{universe radius}}} = \sqrt{\frac{1.704157 \times 10^{53} \cdot 6.67259 \times 10^{-11}}{1.26521 \times 10^{26}}} = 299\,792\,458 \text{ m/s} \quad (8.4.3)$$

As expected, the result of the calculation (8.4.3) also coincides perfectly with the calculation (7.5.5) and is equal to the constant of the speed of light (c.1).

(8.5.0) Relationship between the cosmic velocity formula and the cosmological constant

The results of the calculations made with the cosmological constant (Nc.2) and with the formula of cosmic velocity (1.3) coincide perfectly, we look for the relationship, we have calculated the density $\rho\zeta$ of the dark matter of the vacuum with the cosmological constant (0nc.2), now we unify the two formulas.

Cosmic velocity Formula (1.2) $(vc)^2 \cdot r = G \cdot M$ we used it in the (8.1.3) that has become

$$\text{Expansion velocity} = \sqrt{\frac{G \cdot \text{dark mater mass } \zeta \text{ (kg)}}{\text{distance (m)}}}$$

to calculate the expansion rate, knowing the dimensions of the vacuum; We integrate the density of dark matter $\rho\zeta$ with the formula (1.2) which becomes;

We replace the symbol (r) radius with (d) for distance and mass (M) becomes the volume formula for density ($V \cdot \rho\zeta$);

$$\text{formula (1.2)} \quad (\text{exp. vel.})^2 \cdot d = G \cdot \left[\frac{4}{3} \pi \cdot (d)^3 \cdot \rho\zeta \right] \quad (8.5.1)$$

$$\text{Which becomes;} \quad (\text{exp. vel.})^2 = \frac{G \cdot \left[\frac{4}{3} \pi \cdot (d)^3 \cdot \rho\zeta \right]}{d}$$

$$(\text{exp. vel.})^2 = G \cdot \left[\frac{4}{3} \pi \cdot (d)^2 \cdot \rho\zeta \right]$$

$$\text{Which becomes the formula (1.3) } (\text{exp. vel.}) = \sqrt{G \cdot \left[\frac{4}{3} \pi \cdot (d)^2 \cdot \rho\zeta \right]}$$

$$\text{we inhaled the values of the constants, } \text{exp. vel.} = \sqrt{6.672 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 2.00878 \times 10^{-26} \cdot 4.188 \cdot (d)^2}$$

$$\text{exp. vel.} = \sqrt{5.61456152 \times 10^{-36} \cdot (d)^2}$$

$$\text{che diventa} \quad \text{exp. vel.} = 2.3695066 \times 10^{-18} \cdot d \quad (8.5.2)$$

The result of the formula (8.5.2) includes the gravitational constant (C.2) and the value of the density of dark matter in a vacuum (Nc.5) The result is the cosmological constant Λ_q (Nc.2), the G constant does not cancel out as in the formulas (7.0.2) and (7.0.5)

(8.6.0) Gravitational interaction between the star Proxima Centauri and the Sun

Let's calculate the interacting values between the mass of the Sun and the mass of the star closest to us, Proxima Centauri, we know the Sun let's mention Proxima Centauri, it is the closest star to the Sun it is a Red dwarf it is smaller than the Sun and visible from Earth and for this reason we have more precise estimates of the star, the distance from the Sun is 4.243 light-years away, its mass is estimated to be 2.193×10^{29} kg, together with the Sun rotates around the center of our galaxy with the average speed of 230 000 meters/second, the two stars approach the estimated speed of 21 500 meters per second, we try to calculate their interactions without taking into account the influences of the other masses.

We calculate with the formula (1.3) the two cosmic velocities, we convert the distance of light years into meters.

$$\text{Distance } 4.243 \text{ light-years} \cdot 9.45425 \times 10^{15} = 4.0114 \times 10^{16} \text{ meters} \quad (8.6.1)$$

$$\text{Mass Proxima Centauri} = 2.193 \times 10^{29} \text{ kg}$$

$$\text{Mass Sun} = 1.989 \times 10^{30} \text{ kg}$$

$$\text{Cosmic speed of the Sun on Proxima Centauri} = \sqrt{\frac{2.193 \times 10^{29} \cdot 6.6725 \times 10^{-11}}{4.0114 \times 10^{16}}} = 57\,520 \text{ m/s} \quad (8.6.2)$$

$$\text{Cosmic speed of Proxima Centauri on the Sun} = \sqrt{\frac{1.989 \times 10^{30} \cdot 6.6725 \times 10^{-11}}{4.0114 \times 10^{16}}} = 19\,100 \text{ m/s} \quad (8.6.3)$$

$$\text{The sum of the two Speeds } 57\,520 + 19\,100 = 76\,620 \text{ m/s} \quad (8.6.4)$$

(8.6.4) is the sum of the two cosmic velocities, the result is more than three times that estimated 21 500 meters, given the size and distance of the two stars they do not rotate around each other, the cosmic velocity becomes the speed of approach, the two stars practically slide towards each other in the field of space-time that they deform with their mass, if they were not influenced by the forces of the other stars and the black hole at the center of the Milky Way.

We calculate the escape velocity, due to the expansion of the space between the two stars;

$$\text{Escape velocity} = 4.0114 \times 10^{16} \cdot 2.369506 \times 10^{-18} = 0.0951 \text{ meters/seconds} \quad (8.6.5)$$

The escape velocity (8.6.4) is negligible compared to the approach velocity.

(9.0) Comparison of calculations and observations of the size of the universe

From the calculations made, observing the boundary of the universe, we cannot see beyond this limit distance, because due to the sum of the acceleration of the expansion of space, the cosmic speed reaches the limiting speed of the speed of light (c.1) at these speeds space contracts towards zero and time stretches towards infinity.

We ask ourselves two questions:

First question: the measured magnitude of the expansion of the space of the visible universe from the Big Bang to the present has been observed to be of the radius of 46.5 billion light years ¹, for a total diameter of the universe of 93 billion light years ¹, not compatible with the data calculated in chapters (8.4.3), perhaps solvable with the answer to the second question,

Second question: does the light emitted by distant stars and galaxies, due to the effect of the expansion of space, come from a greater distance on Earth?

Let's take an example of what we mean, a photon of light emitted by a galaxy that is at a distance of one mega parsec from the earth traveling at the speed of 299 792 458 m/s towards us will face a countercurrent speed due to the expansion of space, when the light travels the last stretch to arrive on Earth the delay is zero, but at the start at the distance of one mega parsec it starts with a counter-current speed of 73 115 km/s, which means that for the entire route it travels an average speed of;

$$\text{Average speed traveled in the last stretch; } \frac{73\,115 \frac{m}{s}}{2} = 36\,557 \text{ m/s} \quad (9.1)$$

Practically for every second of its path it loses 36 557 meters, let's see what it entails for the distance of a mega parsec of time of 3 262 000 years we transform time into seconds, knowing that a year is composed of 31 536 000 seconds, we calculate the delay;

$$\text{Delay} = 3\,262\,000 \cdot 31\,536\,000 \cdot 36\,557 = 3.76063 \times 10^{18} \text{ meters} \quad (9.2)$$

(9.2) is the delay in meters of the path of light, let's transform it into time:

$$\text{delay time} = \frac{3.76063 \times 10^{18}}{299\,792\,458} = 1.25441 \times 10^{10} \text{ seconds} \quad (9.3)$$

$$\text{Let's turn (9.3) into light years} = \frac{1.25441 \times 10^{10}}{31\,536\,000} = 397.77 \text{ Light years} \quad (9.4)$$

The result (9.4) indicates that the light to travel the distance of one mega parsec due to the expansion of space is delayed by 397.77 light years, let's take into consideration that the photon of light starts from a galaxy at a distance of 4 200 mega parsecs (8.4.1) from Earth, practically the last observable before which due to the cosmic speed of expansion reaches the speed of light, where space should close, we can make the calculation considering the average speed that the photon of light must travel in the first mega parsec from departure, we set the calculation for the photon traveling at the speed of light in the direction of the earth, speed $c = 299\,792\,458 \text{ m/s}$; Average expansion rate of the last mega parsec, average velocity $AV = \frac{73\,115 \frac{m}{s}}{2} = 36\,557 \text{ m/s}$ (9.1) Practically the difference between the average expansion speed and the speed of light of the last mega parsec is

$$C - (C - AV) = 299\,792\,458 - (299\,792\,458 - 36\,557) = 299\,792\,458 - 299\,755\,899 = 36\,557 \text{ m/s} \quad (9.1)$$

From the result (9.1) the photon traveling at the speed of light of 299 792 458 m/s in the direction of the Earth must exceed the expansion speed of space of 299 755 899 m/s, being able to travel the last mega parsec only at the average speed of 36 557 m/s accelerating by 36 557 m/s for each mega parsec it travels in the direction of the Earth.

Let's calculate how long it takes for the photon of light to travel the last mega parsec, at the average speed of 36 557 m/s we find the length of a mega parsec (c.12) $3.0856776 \cdot 10^{22}$ meters, we set up the calculation;

$$\text{Time required} = \frac{3.0856776 \times 10^{22} m}{36\,557 \frac{m}{s}} = 8.44 \times 10^{17} \text{ seconds}, \quad (9.5)$$

$$\text{We convert seconds into years} = \frac{8.44 \times 10^{17}}{31\,536\,000} = 2.676 \times 10^{10} \text{ years} \quad (9.6)$$

equal to 26.76 billion years, conclusion to the photon of light to travel the first mega parsec due to the effect of expanding space it takes the same years calculated for the magnitude of visible space with the formula of special relativity.

Knowing that the average speed of the photon of light increases by 36 557 m/s for each parsec it travels towards the Earth at the penultimate parsec the average speed will be formula 73 115 m/s, we set the formula

$$\frac{3.0856776 \times 10^{22} m}{73\,115 \frac{m}{s}} = 4.22 \times 10^{17} s = \frac{4.22 \times 10^{17}}{31\,536\,000} = 1.338 \times 10^{10} \text{ Years} \quad (9.7)$$

Equal to 13.38 billion years, if the calculations are correct the real observable space is much larger than expected, the sum of the years of the first two parsecs is more than 40 billion light years, at this rate comes an extreme measure, to overcome this dilemma we have taken advantage of the artificial intelligence program Copilot, on February 9, 2024

The answer:

Thus, it would take about 137.3 billion years for a photon of light to travel 4,200 mega parsecs in the expanding universe.

The result of the answer deserves further study that will not be dealt with in this work.

(10.0) The size of a white hole calculated with the density of dark matter $\rho\zeta$

White holes have never been observed, they are predicted in general relativity, it is a hypothetical region of spacetime, a singularity that cannot be entered from the outside, but from which energy-matter and light can come out. In this sense, it is the opposite of the black hole, which can only be entered and from which neither energy nor light can escape. As calculated in chapter 4.0 on black holes, with the formula (4.0.3) we can find the radius of a black or white hole, finding the maximum size for a mass for which the peripheral velocity reaches the limiting velocity of the cosmic velocity (Nc.4).

$$\text{Formula for Calculating the Radius } r \text{ of a Black or White Hole } (r) = \sqrt{\frac{c^2}{4.188 \cdot 2G \cdot \rho}} \text{ meters} \quad (4.0.3)$$

Knowing the density of the vacuum, from the result of the expansion of space. The maximum observable effect is the opposite of the speed of attraction, we can set the equation to find the

maximum radius of a white hole with the density of dark matter contained in the void (Nc.5) = $2,008781976 \cdot 10^{-26} \frac{kg}{m^3}$ and we put it in the formula (4.0.3).

$$\text{White Hole Radius } r = \sqrt{\frac{c^2}{4.188 \cdot 2G \cdot 2.008781976 \cdot 10^{-26}}} = 8,9464 \cdot 10^{25} \text{ meters} \quad (10.1)$$

Let's convert the radius from meters to light years, one light year = $9,461 \cdot 10^{15}$ meters

$$\text{We calculate } \frac{8,9464 \cdot 10^{25}}{9,461 \cdot 10^{15}} = 9,4628 \cdot 10^9 \text{ years} = 9,462 \text{ billion years}, \quad (10.2)$$

The result (10.1) and (10.2) are the maximum size of a white hole, unlike a black hole nothing can penetrate it from the outside.

(11.0) Calculation of the wavelength and frequency from the mass and energy of dark matter contained in empty space in relation to the cosmological constant and the Ricci scalar

In the previous chapters we have calculated the values of the expansion velocity starting from the measurement of one meter and we have arrived at the maximum limit distance of the observable universe, now we analyze the data we have processed and compare them at the quantum level, therefore we compare the density of dark matter with Planck's formulas, we have calculated the energy of the mass of dark matter contained in one cubic meter of empty space, with Einstein's formula (5.1.1)) $E = M \cdot C^2$;

$$\text{Energy in joule } E\zeta = 2.008781976 \cdot 10^{-26} \cdot c^2 = 1.8054 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ joule } m^3, \quad (\text{Nc.6})$$

Having the energy, we calculate the frequency and wavelength of dark matter with formulas;

$$\text{Frequency formula} \quad E = h \cdot f \quad f = \frac{E}{h} \quad (11.1)$$

$$\text{Wavelength formula} \quad \lambda = \frac{1}{f} \quad (11.2)$$

In which (E) is the energy in joule, (h) is the constant of Planck $6.626 \cdot 10^{-34}$ and f is the frequency in Herz (Hz)

$$\text{Dark matter frequency } (f\zeta) = \frac{1.8054 \cdot 10^{-9}}{6.626 \cdot 10^{-34}} = 2.7247 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ Hz}, \quad (11.3)$$

The result of (11.3) is the frequency for the density of the dark matter mass of one cubic meter of space and as a new value we have assigned it the number (Nc.7) and the symbol ($f\zeta$)

$$\text{Dark matter wavelength} = \lambda\zeta = \frac{1}{f} = 3.6701 \cdot 10^{-25} \text{ meters} \quad (11.4)$$

(11.4) represents the wavelength but also the minimum length of expansion of space for each frequency and as a new value we have assigned it the number (Nc.8) and the symbol $\lambda\zeta$

With the processed data we calculate the space produced by the velocity of the cosmological constant (Nc.2) = $1q2.3695066 \times 10^{-18}$ m/s of one square meter of space, for the wavelength, we calculated that the energy of the mass of the vacuum produces in one second 2.7247×10^{24} frequencies (11.3), each of a wavelength of 3.6701×10^{-25} meters, we see the volume produced for each frequency, we set the formula;

$$1q \cdot m^2 \cdot \lambda = \text{expansion velocity (m/s)} \cdot \text{square meters (m} \cdot \text{m)} \cdot \lambda \text{ (m/s)} = \frac{m^4}{s^2}$$

We enter the values into the formula;

$$\text{volume} = 2.369506 \times 10^{-18} \text{ m/s} \cdot (1\text{m} \cdot 1\text{m}) \cdot 3.6701 \times 10^{-25} \text{ m/s} = 8.69641 \times 10^{-43} = \frac{m^4}{s^2} \quad (11.5)$$

$$\text{or} = 1q \cdot m^2 \cdot \frac{1}{f} = \frac{12.369506 \times 10^{-18} \text{ m/s} \cdot (1\text{m} \cdot 1\text{m}) \cdot 1}{2.7247 \times 10^{24}} = 8.69641 \times 10^{-43} = \frac{m^2}{s} \quad (11.6)$$

The result of (11.5) represents a volume of expansion in four spatial dimensions, accelerated, or one surface per second, we see the relations of (11.5) and (11.6) with the part of the formula (6.2) of the Ricci scalar (c.11).

Let's take the part of the Ricci scalar and convert the constants into numbers;

$$\text{Ricci's scalar} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} = \frac{8(3.14) \cdot 6.67259 \times 10^{-11}}{(299\,792\,458)^4} = 2.076115 \times 10^{-4} \quad (11.7)$$

Let's take the value of the calculation (11.5) and divide them by the value of the Ricci scalar (11.7).

$$\text{equal to } \frac{8.69641 \times 10^{-43}}{2.076115 \times 10^{-4}} = 4.188; \quad \frac{8.69641 \times 10^{-43}}{4.188} = \frac{8.69641 \times 10^{-4}}{\frac{4}{3}\pi} = 2.076115 \times 10^{-43} \quad (11.7)$$

The result (11.7) indicates that the value of the Ricci scalar is the volume of the radius cubed of a sphere.

Let's check the calculation (11.3), the energy for each frequency;

$$\text{Energy for each frequency } E = \frac{1.8054 \times 10^{-9} \text{ joule } m^3}{2.7247 \times 10^{24} \text{ Hz}} = 6.626 \times 10^{-34} \text{ joule} \cdot \text{seconds} \quad (11.8)$$

The result of the calculation (11.9) is equal to the value of Planck's constant h (c.3), the minimum value, which means that the energy intensity for each frequency cannot be less than the calculated value of (11.3)

(12.0) The Quantum Rhythm of Space Expansion

We found the following physical characteristics of dark matter contained in empty space, the density $\rho\zeta$ the mass $M\zeta$, energy $E\zeta$, the wavelength $\lambda\zeta$ and frequency $f\zeta$, we have found a constant for the expansion of space that agrees with all observations, we report the values of empty space and relate them to the cosmological constant of expansion to find the quantum rate of expansion.

The values of dark matter per cubic meter of empty space;

Frequency	$f\zeta$	2.7247×10^{24}	Hz
Wavelength	$\lambda\zeta$	3.67015×10^{-25}	m/s
Mass density	$\rho\zeta$	2.00878×10^{-26}	kg/m ³
Energy	$E\zeta$	1.8054×10^{-9}	joule m ³

In chapter 11.0 we calculated how the minimum energy limit corresponds to the value of Planck's constant, we calculated that the frequencies of a cubic meter of vacuum cannot be higher than $h2.7247 \times 10^{24}$ Hz and the wavelength not less than 3.67015×10^{-25} meters

We have calculated that empty space expands for every meter for each spatial dimension at the rate of the cosmological constant (Nc.2) $2,3695066 \times 10^{-18}$ meters/sec and we assumed that the converted dark matter is equal to the quantum mass $M\zeta$ 7.3725×10^{-51} kg

$$\text{Energy for space per second } E = \frac{1.8054 \times 10^{-9} \text{ joule } m^3}{2.7247 \times 10^{24} \text{ Hz}} = 6.626 \times 10^{-34} \text{ joule} \cdot \text{sec.} \quad (11.9)$$

The cadence of the rate of expansion is indicated in the number of times that the value of the minimum wavelength pulsates in the value of the cosmological constant, we set the formula;

$$\text{Rhythm} = \frac{\text{cosmological constant}}{\text{wavelength}} = \frac{2.369506 \times 10^{-1} \text{ m/s}}{3.67015 \times 10^{-25} \text{ m/s}} = 6456182 \text{ quantum pulsations} \quad (12.1)$$

The result (12.1) is the number of pulses of Planck quanta per second, it is a new constant we assign the number to it (Nc.9). We calculate the energy emitted by the expansion per square meter of space, just multiply the number of pulses by Planck's constant.

$$\text{Expansion energy for } m^2 = 6456182 \cdot 6.626 \times 10^{-34} = 4.27791 \times 10^{-27} \text{ joules} \cdot \text{seconds} \cdot m^2 \quad (12.2)$$

(12.2) is a new value: we assign it the number (Nc.10), we calculate how much matter is converted into energy per cubic meter for every spatial dimension;

Dark mass converted to dark energy for per second for one square meter .

$$\text{Converted mass for } m^2 = \frac{4.27791 \times 10^{-27}}{(299792458)^2} = 4.75982 \times 10^{-4} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{sec} \cdot m^2 \quad (12.3)$$

The result (12.3) is a new value: we assign it the number (Nc.11). we calculate how much dark mass is converted into dark energy for each individual drive;

$$\text{Dark mass converted to energy per pulsations} = \frac{4.75982 \times 10^{-4}}{6456182} = 7,372503 \times 10^{-51} \text{ kg} \quad (12.4)$$

The result (12.4) is the value of the mass of dark matter that equals the quantum mass (Nc.1) is consistent with forecasts.

The values calculated in (12.2) and (12.3) are valid for a surface area of one square meter, to calculate the expansion of a three-dimensional space we take the value of the surface area of the sphere of the radius of one meter and divide it by the volume of a sphere of the radius of one material, we calculate the ratio;

$$\text{ratio} = \frac{4\pi \cdot r^2}{\frac{4}{3}\pi \cdot r^3} = \frac{12.566 \cdot 1 \cdot 1}{4.188 \cdot 1 \cdot 1 \cdot 1} = 3 \quad (12.5)$$

(12.5) tells us the ratio of the expansion of the surface in square meters in relation to the volume in cubic meters, now we can calculate how much dark mass is converted into dark energy for each second in the expansion of the universe, let's take up the volume of the universe (8.4.1) = $8.483536 \times 10^{78} m^3$ and we multiply it by the mass converted into energy per square meter we multiply by the calculated ratio (12.5)

$$(8.48353 \times 10^{78} \cdot 4.75982 \times 10^{-44} \cdot 3) = 1.2114 \times 10^{36} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{second} \quad (12.6)$$

With the result (12.6) we calculated that in the universe in every second are converted, That's equivalent of about 609 000 solar masses of dark matter in dark energy.

(13.0) Planck's length, time and mass

We calculate the maximum and minimum wavelength for an electromagnetic wave, for this we use the Planck length l_p , Planck's time t_p , Planck mass m_p and quantum mass M_q , let's compare the length, time and Planck mass and quantum mass (Nc.1) we start from the Planck length is obtained starting from the Compton wavelength equation λ_c in which M_0 is the Planck mass m_p (13.3) to which we calculate the Compton wavelength λ_c , theoretically a particle with mass cannot reach the speed of light¹.

Planck mass m_p is a theoretical mass that, when reached the speed of light, produces a Compton wavelength equal to the Planck length l_p , remember that the Compton wavelength is a quantum-mechanical property of a particle¹, was introduced by Arthur Compton¹, concerns the scattering of photons by electrons¹, remember that the Compton wavelength¹ for an electron of mass $9.109 \times 10^{-31} \text{ kg}$ is $2.426 \times 10^{-12} \text{ meters}$, to calculate the Planck values we need to retrieve another constant, the crossed Planck constant $\hbar = 1,055 \times 10^{-34} \text{ (c.4)}$

$$\text{The formula for the Compton wavelength } \lambda_c ; \quad \lambda_c = \frac{h}{M_0 \cdot c} \quad (13.1)$$

$$\text{The formula for calculating Planck mass } m_p = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar \cdot C}{G}} \quad (13.2)$$

$$m_p = \sqrt{\frac{1.055 \times 10^{-34} \cdot 299\,792\,458}{6.67259 \times 10^{-11}}} = 2.176 \times 10^{-8} \text{ kg} \quad (c.5)$$

$$l_p = \lambda_c = \frac{6.626 \times 10^{-34}}{2.176 \times 10^{-8} \cdot 299\,792\,458} = 1.61605 \times 10^{-35} \text{ meters} \quad (c.6)$$

Length (13.4) is the minimum wavelength for a mass traveling at the speed of light.

Once we have found the minimum Compton wavelength, we calculate the maximum Compton wavelength, for this we need the minimum mass that we have calculated for each quanta.

quantum mass $M_q = 7.3725033 \times 10^{-51} \text{kg}$ (Nc.1) and we put it in the formula (13.1)

$$\lambda_c = \frac{h}{M_q \cdot c} = \frac{6.626 \times 10^{-34}}{7.3725033 \times 10^{-51} \cdot 299\,792\,458} = 299\,792\,458 \text{ meters} \quad (\text{c.1}) \quad (13.3)$$

From the result of (13.3) the Compton wavelength for quantum mass M_q is the maximum wavelength for an electromagnetic wave is equal to the value of the constant of the speed of light (Nc.1), in summary we can write the following characteristics for quantum mass M_q considered as a particle;

Mass $M_q = 7.3725033 \times 10^{-51} \text{ kg}$; Energy $E = 6.626 \times 10^{-34} \text{ joule}$;

Compton wavelength $\lambda_c = 299\,792\,458 \text{ meters}$

We report Planck's formulas to calculate Planck's length l_p and Planck's time t_p

The formula for calculating Planck length $l_p = \sqrt{\frac{G \cdot \hbar}{c^3}}$ we enter the values (13.4)

$$l_p = \sqrt{\frac{6.67259 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 1.055 \times 10^{-34}}{(299\,792\,458)^3}} = 1.61605 \times 10^{-35} \text{ meters} \quad (\text{c.6})$$

Let's write the extended formula (13.4) as the formula (1.2) $(vc)^2 \cdot r = M \cdot G$

the (9.6) $l_p = \sqrt{\frac{G \cdot \hbar}{c^3}}$ becomes; $c^3 \cdot (l_p)^2 = \hbar \cdot G$ (13.5)

Now let's substitute in the formula c^3 with c^2 , and $(l_p)^2$ with l_p and \hbar with Planck mass m_p

The (13.5) becomes; $c^2 \cdot l_p = m_p \cdot G$ we obtain l_p (13.6)

$$l_p = \frac{m_p \cdot G}{c^2} ; l_p = \frac{2.176 \times 10^{-8} \cdot 6.67259 \times 10^{-11}}{(299\,792\,458)^2} = 1.61605 \times 10^{-35} \text{ meters} \quad (\text{c.6})$$

The result of the calculation (13.6) with the formula for cosmic velocity (1.2) is perfectly matched with the result of the length (c.6)

the formula for Planck time is $t_p = \sqrt{\frac{G \cdot \hbar}{c^5}}$ (13.7)

$$t_P = \sqrt{\frac{6.67259 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 1.055 \times 10^{-34}}{(299\,792\,458)^5}} = 5.39056 \times 10^{-44} \text{ seconds} \quad (c.7)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{h}{c} \text{ (9.13)}; t_P = \frac{h}{c} = \frac{6.626 \times 10^{-34}}{299\,792\,458} = 5.39056 \times 10^{-44} \text{ seconds}$$

$$\text{Or replacing } c^2 \text{ with } c^3 \text{ the new formula becomes } t_P = \frac{m_P \cdot G}{c^3} \quad (13.8)$$

$$t_P = \frac{2.176 \times 10^{-8} \cdot 6.67259 \times 10^{-11}}{(299\,792\,458)^3} = 5.39056 \times 10^{-44} \text{ seconds} \quad (c7)$$

(14.0.0) The Schwarzschild radius area and the Planck area

Let's calculate the Schwarzschild radius and area and the Planck area, as we know Schwarzschild assigns each mass a radius by means of his formula $r_s = \frac{2G}{c^2} M$ we calculate the Schwarzschild radius for quantum mass we set the formula by substituting M with M_q .

$$r_s = \frac{2G}{c^2} M_q = \frac{2 \cdot 6.67259 \times 10^{-11}}{(299\,792\,458)^2} \cdot 7.3725033 \times 10^{-51} = 1.0947 \times 10^{-77} \text{ meters} \quad (14.0.1)$$

We found the Schwarzschild radius for quantum mass is a measurement with a length much smaller than the Planck length l_P , we look at Planck values, we know the length, time and Planck mass, we look for a relationship between the Schwarzschild radius of quantum mass and Planck values. Let's start by looking for an infinitesimal point by making the product of the Planck length in meters l_P (c.6) and Planck's time in seconds t_P (c.7), we can define it as an area of space-time, so we indicate it with the symbol, Planck area a_P .

we set up the calculation of the Planck area; $a_P = l_P \cdot t_P = \text{meters} \cdot \text{seconds}$

$$a_P = l_P \cdot t_P = 1.61605 \times 10^{-35} \cdot 5.39056 \times 10^{-44} = 8.7114 \times 10^{-79} \text{ meters} \cdot \text{seconds}; \quad (14.0.2)$$

Since the result (14.0.2) is a value of two constants, we consider it a new constant (Nc.12)

An infinitesimal value, let's make the ratio between Schwarzschild radius r_s (14.0.1) that we have calculated for quantum mass M_q and the Planck area a_P (14.0.2)

$$\text{ratio} = \frac{r_s \text{ of the } M_q}{a_P} = \frac{1,0947 \times 10^{-77}}{8,7114 \times 10^{-79}} = 12.556 = 4\pi, \quad (14.0.3)$$

The result is a part of the formula for calculating the surface area of a sphere, $S = 4\pi \cdot r^2$ we found a relationship between the Schwarzschild radius of quantum mass and the Planck spacetime area a_P . Now let's look for a relationship with the minimum mass with the minimum energy that we already have in the Planck constant crossed out $\hbar = \frac{h}{2\pi}$, we report Ricci's scalar $\frac{8\pi G}{c^4}$ which is the energy-

impulse tensor, of Einstein's field equation, we calculate its numerical value, to simplify we name it S_R (Ricci's scalar), we recalculate its value;

$$\text{value of } S_R = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} = \frac{8 \cdot (3,14) \cdot 6.67259 \times 10^{-11}}{(299\,792\,458)^4} = 2.076115 \times 10^{-43} \quad (\text{c.11})$$

To find an infinitesimal value of energy, we calculate the value of the product between the Ricci scalar S_R and Planck's constant crossed out \hbar (c.4)

$$S_R \cdot \hbar = 2.076115 \times 10^{-43} \cdot 1.055 \times 10^{-34} = 2.1894 \times 10^{-77} \quad (\text{14.0.4})$$

Let's see the relationship between the results of (14.4) and the Schwarzschild radius r_s (14.1) for quantum mass M_q .

$$\text{ratio} = \frac{S_R \cdot \hbar}{r_s \text{ of the } M_q} = \frac{2.1894 \times 10^{-77}}{1.0947 \times 10^{-77}} = 2 \quad (\text{14.0.5})$$

The result of (14.0.5) is twice the Schwarzschild radius of quantum mass, practically it is the diameter, from this result we can deduce that there is a relationship between space, time, mass and energy, all have a relationship with a surface of a sphere, we rewrite the Schwarzschild formula, with the premise that we no longer divide by the constant c^2 but for a surface of a sphere having a radius equal to the measure of the constant of light. We assign the symbol to the new formula a_s Schwarzschild area, remember that the formula of the surface of the sphere is $S = 4\pi \cdot r^2$

$$\text{The formula } r_s = \frac{2G}{c^2} M_q \text{ becomes } a_s = \frac{2G}{4\pi \cdot c^2} M_q \quad (\text{14.0.6})$$

The formula (14.0.6) describes the following calculation, twice the gravitational Gconstant divided by the surface of a sphere that has the value of the light constant as its radius. (c.1)

$$a_s = \frac{2G}{4\pi \cdot c^2} M_q = \frac{2 \cdot 6.67259 \times 10^{-11}}{4\pi \cdot (299\,792\,458)^2} \cdot 7.3725033 \times 10^{-51} = 8,7114 \times 10^{-77} \frac{2 \cdot \left(\frac{m^3}{kg \cdot s^2}\right) \cdot kg}{m^2} \quad (\text{14.0.7})$$

The value of the result (14.0.7) of the Schwarzschild area is equal to the result of (14.0.2) which is the value of the area of Planck's spacetime a_s and we assign it as a new constant the number (Nc.13).

(14.1.0) Relationship between the Planck area and the Schwarzschild area with quantum mass and dark matter density $\rho\zeta$

In the previous chapters we have seen the equality of the values of the Planck area and the Schwarzschild area, let's do other calculations with the formula (14.0.6)

Let's rewrite the two values;

for the Planck space-time area (Nc.12); $a_P = 8.7114 \times 10^{-7}$ meters · seconds

for the Schwarzschild area (Nc.13).; $a_S = 8,7114 \times 10^{-79} \frac{2 \cdot \left(\frac{m^3}{kg \cdot s^2}\right) \cdot kg}{m^2}$

We recalculate the Schwarzschild area for quantum mass M_q ;

$$a_S = \frac{2G}{4\pi \cdot c^2} M_q = \frac{2 \cdot 6.67259 \times 10^{-11}}{4\pi \cdot (299\,792\,458)^2} \cdot 7.3725033 \times 10^{-51} = 8.7114 \times 10^{-79} \frac{2 \cdot \left(\frac{m^3}{kg \cdot s^2}\right) \cdot kg}{m^2} \quad (14.1.1)$$

We calculate the Schwarzschild area for the density of dark matter $\rho\zeta$

$$a_S = \frac{2G}{4\pi \cdot c^2} \rho\zeta = \frac{2 \cdot 6.67259 \times 10^{-11}}{4\pi \cdot (299\,792\,458)^2} \cdot 2.0087819 \times 10^{-26} = 2.37359 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2 \quad (14.1.2)$$

Let's calculate the ratio of the Schwarzschild area a_S of quantum mass M_q , and the area a_S of dark matter density $\rho\zeta$

$$\text{ratio} = \frac{2.37359 \times 10^{-54}}{8,7114 \times 10^{-79}} = 2.7247 \times 10^{24} \quad (14.1.3)$$

The ratio of the results (14.1.2) and (14.1.3) is equal to the frequency $f\zeta$ of dark matter (nc.7)

14.2.0 Relationship between the Schwarzschild area divider and the dielectric permittivity of the vacuum ϵ_0

Electrical permittivity (or dielectric constant)¹ is a physical quantity that measures the tendency of a material to counteract the intensity of an electric field within it¹, indicating the ability of a substance to polarize in response to an applied field¹, influencing energy storage¹.

It is divided into absolute ϵ and related $\epsilon_r = \frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_0}$;

The constant of the dielectric permittivity of vacuum $\epsilon_0 = 8.854188 \times 10^{-12}$ Farad/meters (14.2.1)

$$1 \text{ Farad}^1 = \frac{\text{Coulomb}}{\text{Volt}} = \frac{\text{Ampere} \cdot \text{secondi}}{\text{Volt}} = \frac{s^4 \cdot A^2}{m^2 \cdot kg}$$

Let's calculate the value of the divisor of the Schwarzschild area formula, remember that the divisor represents the area of the surface of a sphere with the radius the velocity c of the constant of light;

$$\text{Divider} = 4\pi \cdot c^2 = 4(3.14) \cdot (299\,792\,458)^2 = 1.12941 \times 10^{18} \text{ m}^2 \quad (14.2.2)$$

Let's calculate the inverse value of the divided

$$\text{inverse value} = \frac{1}{1.12941 \times 10^{18}} = 8.854188 \times 10^{-19} \quad (14.2.3)$$

Let's calculate the ratio of (14.2.3) to the dielectric constant ϵ_0 (14.2.1).

$$\text{ratio} = \frac{8.854188 \times 10^{-19}}{8.854188 \times 10^{-12}} = 1 \times 10^{-7} \quad (14.2.4)$$

we can rewrite; Planck area a_p equal Schwarzschild area $a_s = \frac{2G \cdot M}{4\pi \cdot c^2} =$

$$= \frac{2G \cdot M}{1} = \frac{2G \cdot M}{1 \times 10^{-7} \cdot 8.854 \times 10^{-12}} = \frac{2G \cdot M}{1 \times 10^{-7} \cdot \epsilon_0} = 1 \times 10^{-7} \cdot \epsilon_0 \cdot (2G \cdot M)$$

$$a_s \text{ with vacuum permittivity} = 1 \times 10^{-7} \cdot \epsilon_0 \cdot (2G \cdot M) \quad (14.2.5)$$

Calculating the value with quantum mass $= 1 \times 10^{-7} \cdot \epsilon_0 \cdot (2G \cdot M_q)$

$$\text{Value} = 1 \times 10^{-7} \cdot 8.854188 \times 10^{-12} \cdot (2 \cdot 6.67259 \times 10^{-11} \cdot 7.3725033 \times 10^{-51}) = 8.7114 \times 10^{-7}$$

$$= 8.7114 \times 10^{-79} \frac{\text{Farad}}{\text{m}} \cdot \frac{2 \cdot \left(\frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{kg} \cdot \text{s}^2}\right) \cdot \text{kg}}{\text{m}^2} \quad (14.2.6)$$

From the formulas (14.0.2) (14.0.7) (14.2.5) a relationship between the Planck area emerges a_p , the Schwarzschild area a_s and the dielectric constant of the vacuum ϵ_0 .

(15.0) Quantification of the matter of the universe by adding visible baryonic matter, invisible dark matter and dark energy

It has been estimated that the universe is composed of 4.9% visible baryonic matter, 26.8% dark matter and 68.3% dark energy, the latter invisible, in the previous chapters we calculated that the total mass of dark matter is equal to 1.704157×10^{53} kg (8.4.2) Since dark matter represents 26.8% of the matter in the universe, let's calculate the value of the other masses.

$$\text{Dark energy mass equal to } 26.8\% = 1.704157 \times 10^{53} \text{ kg} \quad (8.4.2)$$

$$\text{Baryonic matter mass equal to } 4.9\% = \frac{1.704157 \times 10^{53}}{26.8} \cdot 4.9 = 3.11581 \times 10^{52} \text{ kg} \quad (15.1)$$

$$\text{Dark energy equal to } 68.3\% = \frac{1.704157 \times 10^{53}}{26.8} \cdot 68.3 = 4.43058 \times 10^{53} \text{ kg} \quad (15.2)$$

$$\text{Total mass} = 1.704157 \times 10^{53} + 4.343058 \times 10^{53} + 3.11581 \times 10^{52} = 6.35879 \times 10^{53} \text{ kg} \quad (15.3)$$

The total mass of visible baryonic matter (15.1) = $3.11581 \times 10^{52} \text{ kg}$, if the calculations are correct, the result is about a third of the estimated one 10^{53} kg .¹

The result of (15.3) is the presumed sum of the total mass of matter in the universe.

(16.0) The state of space and raw material of the Big Bang

In this paragraph we try to give a dimension to the state of matter and space before the Big Bang, matter is assumed to have been in a singularity condition, we have the minimum mass calculated with the particle of quantum mass M_q (NC.1) and the minimum dimensions that are, the Planck length l_p (13.7). We calculate the volume of space of a sphere with the radius of the Planck length, we enter the Planck length as the radius in the volume formula of a sphere; $V = \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3$ formula for minimum Volume of a Sphere = $\frac{4}{3} \pi (l_p)^3$

$$\text{Minimum volume for a sphere} = \frac{4}{3} \cdot 3.14159 \cdot (1.61605 \times 10^{-35})^3 = 1.7678 \times 10^{-104} \text{ m}^3 \quad (16.1)$$

$$\text{Weight of quantum mass } M_q = 7.3725033 \times 10^{-51} \text{ kg} \quad (\text{Nc.1})$$

With these two data we can calculate the density of quantum mass for the volume of a sphere of the size of the radius of the Planck length, with the formula $\rho \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$;

$$\text{Density } \rho = \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3} = \frac{7.3725 \times 10^{-51}}{1.7678 \times 10^{-104}} = 4.7041 \times 10^{53} \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3} \quad (16.2)$$

Practically a sphere with a volume of one cubic meter, with a diameter of about 1.24 meters, has a mass greater than the baryonic mass (mass of subatomic particles protons, neutrons and electrons) of the entire visible universe, estimated to be, on the 10^{53} kg .¹ Calculated by us in $3.11581 \times 10^{52} \text{ kg}$

We have calculated that the total mass of the universe should be $6.35879 \times 10^{53} \text{ kg}$ (15.3).

The result (16.2) deals with a singularity, the weight of quantum mass divided by the minimum volume of a sphere, calculated with the radius of the Planck length could have been the condition of primordial matter, before the Big Bang.

Conclusion

In this work I have tried to define a physical mechanism that explains the action of the expansion of space, I have hypothesized the action of dark matter which, slowly converting into dark energy, performs a work, calculable in joules, that could explain the phenomenon.

I took into consideration the law of universal gravitation that explains the phenomenon of attraction well to give a link to the phenomenon of repulsion, in order to be able to formulate a law contrary to gravity, I started from the formula of cosmic velocity, speed caused by the space-time deformation of the masses of celestial bodies, with the limit of deformation I came to write a formula to calculate the size of black holes in relation to the density of the matter of which it is presumed to be composed.

In the theory I propose, I try to interpret the mechanics of the action that causes the expansion of space. The calculations showed that the expansion follows a very precise rhythm that can be traced back to the values of Planck quanta at an infinitesimal level.

The evidence that expansion increases with the increase of distance and consequently of the volume of space, suggests that the cause of the action must depend on an intrinsic physical characteristic of empty space, a characteristic that seems to have in common with gravity its law for calculating cosmic velocity, with the difference that the action is one of expansion.

The hypothesis that it is dark matter that slowly disintegrating into dark energy, causes the work of the expansion of space, led me to find new formulas and to perform calculations to find a constant of the expansion of space, with the constant I was able to calculate the physical characteristics of the matter contained in space, obtaining its density, the mass, energy, wavelength, and frequency that leads to a quantum rate of expansion. I adapted some formulas and set up specific equations as listed below.

I adapted Newton's equation of universal gravitation to derive cosmic velocity with the Schwarzschild radius formula to find the upper limit of cosmic velocity.

With cosmic speed at the limit, I was able to derive an equation to calculate the size of black holes based on the density of matter.

I calculated a theoretical minimum mass, the quantum mass with which it assigns a mass to each quantum of Planck's constant using Einstein's mass-energy equivalence equation, inserting Planck's constant instead of energy, I believe that both the dark matter contained in space is homogeneously distributed in space at such an infinitesimal level that they cannot be absorbed and therefore tracked by electromagnetic waves and therefore remain invisible dark .

I inserted the value of quantum mass in the formula of cosmic velocity instead of mass and making the product with the universal gravitational constant I integrated it into a part of Einstein's formula of general relativity in which he calculates the cosmological constant, in particular I needed the value of Ricci's scalar, from the calculation emerged a value of a cosmological constant that describes the expansion of space perfectly compatible with the measurements is a velocity in meters per second that I called the quantum cosmological constant, with which I could calculate a value for the Hubble constant, which I called the quantum Hubble constant.

From the expansion speed of the quantum cosmological constant I was able to calculate the physical values of the matter contained in empty space such as density, mass, energy, frequency and wavelength.

From the density of dark matter, using the formula to calculate black holes, I was able to calculate the maximum size of a white hole.

From the wavelength and frequency I could calculate the quantum rate of expansion of space per meter per second and the amount of dark matter mass converted into energy for each pulse, the result is equivalent to the value of the quantum mass and the energy of a Planck quantum.

I looked for a relationship between Planck values such as length and time, finding the Planck area a space-time value from the product of the Planck length times Planck time, which is related to the emerged value of the Schwarzschild radius of quantum mass, by modifying the Schwarzschild formula I found an equivalence of the values of the Planck area with the Schwarzschild area.

I found that the inverse of the divisor of the Schwarzschild area formula is a submultiple of the dielectric constant of the vacuum, I rewrote the equation of the new formula and I am sure that it deserves further investigation to find the exact relationship.

With the density of dark matter, knowing the size of the universe I could calculate the total mass of dark matter and knowing the percentage of dark matter compared to dark energy and visible baryonic matter I could also calculate their masses.

All the verifications of the calculations have proved to be congruent with the observations, and opens new avenues of in-depth study in the field of the limit of the observability of the universe, where the observations do not coincide with the calculations, and in the field of the limit of the infinitesimal values of the Planck and Schwarzschild area where the calculations show coincidences that cannot be random. And it deserves further study for a possible relationship between the Schwarzschild and Planck areas and the dielectric constant of the vacuum permittivity ϵ_0 .

Table of Physical constants:

Everything that is marked with the superscript 1¹ has been detected by <https://it.wikipedia.org> and <https://google.com>

All calculations were performed with the program Microsoft Excel;

The constants shown in the table below are those recommended in 1986 at the CODATA. Tavola delle costanti Fisiche Fondamentali, <http://www.lamm.unifi.it/tabelle/costa.htm>

More information can be found on the website: <http://physics.nist.gov/PhisRefData/codata86/codata86.html>

c.1 ; Speed of light in a vacuum	(c)	299 792 458 $m s^{-1}$
c.2 ; Newtonian Constant of Gravitation	(G)	6.67259 $\times 10^{-11} m^3 k_g^{-1} s^{-2}$
c.3 ; Planck's constant	(h)	6.6260755 $\times 10^{-34} Js$
c.4 ; h - tagliata	($h - bar$)	1.0545726 $\times 10^{-34} Js$
c.5 ; Planck mass	(m_p)	2.17671 $\times 10^{-8} k_g$
c.6 ; Planck length	(l_p)	1.61605 $\times 10^{-35} m$
c.7 ; Planck Time	(t_p)	5.39056 $\times 10^{-44} s$

Other constants:

c.8 ; Hubble constant	(H_0)	67.4 -76.5 $km s^{-1}$
c.9 ; Year Seconds		31 536 000 seconds
c.10 ; Light Year		9.45425 $\times 10^{15} meters$
c.11 ; Ricci's scalar		2.076115 $\times 10^{-43}$
c.12 ; Mega parsec		3.0856776 $\times 10^{22} meters$

New constants, which emerged during this work, with indications of the chapters where they were calculated;

Nc.1 ; Quantum mass	(M_q)	7.3725033 $\times 10^{-51} k_g$	(5.0.3)
Nc.2 ; Quantum cosmological constant	(Λ_q)	2.3695066 $\times 10^{-18} m s^{-1}$	(7.0.4)
Nc.3 ; Quantum Hubble constant	(H_q)	73.116,335 $m s^{-1}$	(7.2.1)
Nc.4 ; Cosmic Speed, Limit	($V_{C- limite}$)	211 985 280 $m s^{-1}$	(4.1.4)
Nc.5 : Dark matter density	(ρ_{ζ})	2.008781976 $\times 10^{-26} k_g m^{-3}$	(8.0.2)
Nc.6 ; Dark matter energy	(E_{ζ})	1.85054 $\times 10^{-9} joule m^3$	(8.0.3)
Nc.7 ; Dark matter frequency	(f_{ζ})	2.7247 $\times 10^{24}$ Hertz	(11.3)
Nc.8 ; Dark matter wavelength	(λ_{ζ})	3.6701 $\times 10^{-25} m$	(11.4)
Nc.9 ; Pace of quantum expansion		6 456 182 Quantum pulsations /s	(12.1)
Nc.10 ; Expansion Energy for m^2		4.27791 $\times 10^{-27}$ joule · seconds · m^2	(12.1)
Nc.11 ; Converted mass for m^2		4.75982 $\times 10^{-44}$ kg · sec · m^2	(12.1)
Nc.12; Area, Planck spacetime	(a_p)	8.7114 $\times 10^{-79}$ meters · seconds;	(14.2)
Nc.13; Schwarzschild sphere area	(a_s)	8.7114 $\times 10^{-7} \frac{2 \cdot \left(\frac{m^3}{kg \cdot s^2} \right) \cdot kg}{m^2}$	(14.7)

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